

Second report on 6G centric enablers

D2.3

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Second report on 6G centric enablers

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Disclaimer

This work has been performed in the framework of the Horizon Europe project DETERMINISTIC6G co-funded by the EU. This information reflects the consortium's view, but the consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of any of the information contained therein. This deliverable has been submitted to the EU commission, but it has not been reviewed, and it has not been accepted by the EU commission yet.

Executive summary

Future 6G networks are expected to play an important role in offering dependable and time-critical connectivity service. Such service will be crucial for many emerging use cases such as adaptive manufacturing and mobile automation, extended reality, and occupational exoskeletons, as envisioned in [DET23-D11]. These use cases require stringent guarantees on Packet Delay (PD) and Packet Delay Variation (PDV). Enabling these capabilities in 6G will be crucial to fulfill the future requirements of these use cases. This document is a second report on a set of enablers centered in the 6G network, building on the concepts and findings from the first report [DET23-D21].

Packet Delay Correction (PDC) is a 6G-centric strategy to reduce or compensate the PDV introduced by 5G-Adv/6G networks. In this report a new PDC method based on periodicity is proposed, whereby also previously defined PDCs are summarized, and their capabilities and scope of application are compared. Also, simulation-based evaluations are reported showing PDC as a solid enabler that ensures bounded PDV in 6G. In the context of dependable time-critical communications, data-driven latency characterization is key to enable network adaptation based on the ability to predict future QoS Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). This document establishes a mathematical definition of predictability, which is crucial in determining the tradeoffs in communication systems using QoS predictors. Furthermore, an analysis is included with various overheads being compared between the centralized and federated latency prediction architectures. Architectural aspects of observability, which are key to achieve dependability, are also discussed. Finally, efficient Radio Access Network (RAN) resource allocation methods are required for dependable time-critical communication that optimize resource efficiency while ensuring latency and reliability requirements. To this end, a RAN scheduling method is proposed to adapt to the application traffic considering its arrival time and periodicity. Additionally, another RAN scheduling strategy is proposed which enhances reliability and availability aspects by combining reinforcement learning with environmental knowledge.

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1 Introduction

The growth of use cases with stringent time-sensitive requirements imply an effort for future mobile networks to comply and adapt to the needs. In this report 6G-centric solutions are explored and proposed to be able to engage in an end-to-end service that asks for time-critical, dependable and predictable communications. Indeed, the aim is to answer the question on how the mobile network can change or adapt to achieve the required performance.

In this second report on 6G-centric enablers we build on the knowledge and solutions from the first report [DET23-D21] and expand to additional novel solutions and provide a deeper analysis in each of the topics studied. To this end, 6G-centric solutions to improve significantly the latency, Packet Delay Variation (PDV), reliability and availability are proposed here. These involve compensation of the 6G-introduced PDV by applying packet delay correction (PDC) methods, or changes related to the 6G Radio Access Network (RAN) scheduling and resource allocation to improve the overall delay, PDV, reliability and availability. Going even further, ways that interactions between the RAN scheduling and the E2E scheduler can take place are discussed.

Another important aspect that will allow for the 6G service adaptation is the ability to predict the network performance under given network conditions via data-driven latency characterization using machine learning and other AI-related tools. Architectural aspects are also studied with regards to different types of learning architectures and their specific strengths. Additionally, architectural aspects are discussed for enabling an observability feature to assess and verify that the performance provided is aligned the agreed service levels.

1.1 DETERMINISTIC6G approach

Digital transformation of industries and society is resulting in the emergence of a larger family of time-critical services with needs for high availability and which present unique requirements distinct from traditional Internet applications like video streaming or web browsing. Time-critical services are already known in industrial automation; for example, an industrial control application that might require an end-to-end “over the loop” (i.e., from the sensor to the controller back to the actuator) latency of 2 ms and with a communication service requirement of 99.9999 % [3GPP23-22261]. But with the increasing digitalization similar requirements are appearing in a growing number of new application domains, such as extended reality, autonomous vehicles, and adaptive manufacturing. The general long-term trend of digitalization leads towards a Cyber-Physical Continuum where the monitoring, control, and maintenance functionality is moved from physical objects (like a robot, a machine, or a tablet device) to a compute platform at some other location, where a digital representation – or digital twin – of the object is operated. Such Cyber Physical System (CPS) applications need a frequent and consistent information exchange between the digital and physical twins. Several technological developments in the ICT-sector drive this transition. The proliferation of (edge-) cloud compute solutions provides new cost-efficient and scalable computing capabilities that are often more efficient to maintain and evolve compared to embedded compute solutions integrated into the physical objects. It also enables the creation of digital twins as a tool for advanced monitoring, prediction, and automation of system components and improved coordination of systems of systems. New techniques based on Machine Learning can be applied in application design, which can operate over large data sets and profit from scalable compute infrastructure. Offloading compute functionality can also reduce spatial footprint, weight, cost, and energy consumption of physical objects, which is in particular important for mobile components, like vehicles, mobile robots, or wearable devices. This

approach leads to an increasing need for communication between physical and digital objects, and this communication can span over multiple communication and computational domains. Communication in this cyber-physical world often includes closed-loop control interactions which can have stringent end-to-end KPIs (e.g., minimum and maximum packet delay) requirements over the entire loop. In addition, many operations may have high criticality, such as business-critical tasks or even safety relevant operations. Therefore, it is required to provide dependable time-critical communication which provides communication service-assurance to achieve the agreed service requirements.

Time-critical communication has mainly been prevalent in industrial automation scenarios with special compute hardware like Programmable Logic Controllers (PLC), and based on proprietary, mutually incompatible wired communication technologies, such as Powerlink and EtherCat, which is limited to local and isolated network domains and configured for a specific purpose of the local applications. With the standardization of Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) and Deterministic Networking (DetNet), similar capabilities are being introduced into the Ethernet and IP networking technologies, which thereby provide a converged multi-service network enabling time-critical applications in a managed network infrastructure allowing for consistent performance with zero packet loss and guaranteed low and bounded latency. The underlying principles are that the network elements (i.e., bridges or routers) and the PLCs can provide a consistent and known performance with negligible stochastic variation, which allows to manage the network configuration to the needs of time-critical applications with known traffic characteristics and requirements. Furthermore, using interchangeable TSN hardware components has economic benefits, avoids vendor lock-in, and enables third-party support for configuration and troubleshooting.

It turns out that several elements in the digitalization journey introduce characteristics that deviate from the assumptions that are considered as baseline in the planning of deterministic networks. There is often an assumption that for compute and communication elements and also for applications any stochastic behavior can be minimized such that the time characteristics of the element can be clearly associated with tight minimum/maximum bounds. Cloud computing provides efficient scalable compute service, but introduces uncertainty in execution times; wireless communication provides flexibility and simplicity, but with inherently stochastic components that lead to packet delay variations exceeding significantly those found in wired counterparts; and applications embrace novel technologies (e.g., Machine Learning (ML)-based or machine-vision-based control) where the traffic characteristics deviate from the strictly deterministic behavior of old-school control. In addition, there will be an increase in dynamic behavior where characteristics of applications and network or compute elements may change over time in contrast to a static behavior, which does not change during runtime. It turns out that these deviations of stochastic characteristics make traditional approaches to planning and configuration of end-to-end time-critical communication networks such as TSN or DetNet fall short in their performance regarding service performance, scalability, and efficiency. Instead, a revolutionary approach to the design, planning, and operation of time-critical networks is needed that fully embraces the variability but also dynamic changes that come at the side of introducing wireless connectivity, cloud compute, and application innovation. DETERMINISTIC6G has as objective to address these challenges, including the planning of resource allocation for diverse time-critical services end-to-end over multiple domains, providing efficient resource usage and a scalable solution [SPS+23].

DETERMINISTIC6G takes a novel approach towards converged future infrastructures for scalable cyber-physical systems deployment. With respect to networked infrastructures, DETERMINISTIC6G advocates (I) the acceptance and integration of stochastic elements (like wireless links and computational elements) with respect to their stochastic behavior captured through either short-term or longer-term envelopes. Monitoring and prediction of KPIs, for instance latency or reliability, can be leveraged to make individual elements plannable despite a remaining stochastic variance. Nevertheless, system enhancements to mitigate stochastic variances in communication and compute elements are also developed. (II) Next, DETERMINISTIC6G attempts the management of the entire end-to-end interaction loop (e.g., the control loop) with the underlying stochastic characteristics, especially embracing the integration of compute elements. (III) Finally, due to unavoidable stochastic degradations of individual elements, DETERMINISTIC6G advocates allowing for adaptation between applications running over such converged and managed network infrastructures. The idea is to introduce flexibility in the application operation such that its requirements can be adjusted at runtime based on prevailing system conditions. This encompasses a larger set of application requirements that (a) can also accept stochastic end-to-end KPIs, and (b) that possibly can adapt end-to-end KPI requirements at run-time in harmonization with the networked infrastructure. DETERMINISTIC6G builds on a notion of time-awareness, by ensuring accurate and reliable time synchronicity while also ensuring security-by-design for such dependable time-critical communications. Generally, a notion of deterministic communication (where all behavior of network and compute nodes and applications is pre-determined) is extended towards dependable time-critical communication, where the focus is on ensuring that the communication (and compute) characteristics are managed in order to provide the KPIs and reliability levels that are required by the application. DETERMINISTIC6G facilitates architectures and algorithms for scalable and converged future network infrastructures that enable dependable time-critical communication end-to-end, across domains and including 6G.

1.2 Objective of the document

The document has four principal objectives:

1. To analyze and evaluate PDC methods. This includes the proposal of a new PDC method, and a discussion on PDCs' scope of application, precision, overhead, and dependency with the type of traffic. This objective aligns with the objective of Work Package 2 (WP2) on "Development of concepts to achieve deterministic communication in 6G, where the packet delay variation through the 6G system can be bounded to a range of 10's of microseconds."
2. To propose a novel predictability mathematical model that aids in the evaluation of the prediction methods, as well as a proposal of a probability-based latency predictions. This objective aligns with the WP2's objective on "Data-driven latency characterization of the 6G wireless network applying machine-learning and inference to estimate the stochastic behavior of latency."
3. To analyze the efficiency of learning architectures and the architectural aspects related to predictions and observability. This objective aligns with the project's objective to "Develop AI/ML based techniques for data-driven latency characterization of 6G wireless systems architectural aspects of integrating AI/ML-based latency predictors in future 5G-Adv/6G systems."
4. To propose solutions to improve latency, reliability, and availability via RAN scheduling approaches. This includes application traffic alignment with the RAN scheduling, RAN scheduling considering environmental information, and interactions between the E2E TSN

scheduling and the RAN scheduling. This objective aligns with the project’s objective to “Design and develop 6G features for deterministic wireless transmission and wireless-friendly enhancements for TSN and DetNet.”

1.3 Relation to other work packages

This deliverable is part of the WP2 and has relation to other technical work packages, as shown in Figure 1.1. To propose 6G-centric enablers for a dependable and time-critical communication, the work in WP2 takes input from WP1 regarding the use cases and applications, their requirements and traffic profiles as provided in D1.1 [DET23-D11], the envisioned DETERMINISTIC6G architecture as analyzed in D1.2 [DET24-D12], as well as the service design reported in D1.3 [DET24-D13]. This deliverable will be a key input to WP1 in order to form the concepts needed for the final report on the DETERMINISTIC6G architecture in the coming deliverable D1.4.

In this deliverable, learnings have been captured from the technical developments in WP3, where multiple aspects are also taken into consideration in WP2 such as the enablers for deterministic communication standards in D3.1 [DET23-D31]. Also, security aspects in D3.2 [DET23-D32] will provide inputs to another WP2 deliverable, namely D2.4. WP3’s deliverable D3.4 [DET24-D34] developed optimized end-to-end (E2E) schedules that considered PDC concepts from D2.1 [DET23-D21]. This shows that results from WP2 in D2.1 which are further developed in this deliverable, are relevant for optimized TSN schedules in WP3. Note that this deliverable includes a study on the interactions between the E2E scheduler and the 6G RAN scheduler for an optimal service. Furthermore, concepts included in this deliverable will be an input to be considered by WP3 in the development of multi-domain E2E schedules for deliverable D3.5.

Figure 1.1 Relation between work packages in DETERMINISTIC6G and relation to this WP2 deliverable

WP2 and WP4 has a tight interaction in order to formalize the validation framework based on the features and concepts developed in WP2, especially regarding packet delay correction (PDC) methods being validated. The results of such validations are included now in this deliverable. Further evaluations for PDC will be continued in WP4 and presented in deliverable D4.5 on the validation of DETERMINISTIC6G concepts.

The results from this deliverable have been disseminated (as part of the WP5 task) in the form of scientific conference papers and has resulted to a 3GPP standardization proposal for a de-jittering functionality in Release 18, which is closely related to the PDC concepts.

1.4 Background on 5G-TSN integration

In this section we introduce the concepts of TSN that will be useful to follow the content of this deliverable which has a strong dependence with the integrated 5G and TSN architecture, as well as TSN features. 5G-TSN integration is the starting point in this section, but concepts are assumed to be applicable for future developments in 5G Advanced and 6G.

TSN enables real-time communication by means of a toolbox of standard capabilities for the bridged Ethernet standard specified in IEEE 802.1 and IEEE 802.3. The TSN toolbox includes functional building blocks, e.g., time synchronization, guaranteed low latency transmissions and high reliability, etc., to enable time-critical communications in Ethernet. The integration of the TSN system into the 5G/6G system provides converged communication on the same network infrastructure for a wide range of services including time-sensitive applications that require deterministic, reliable, and low latency communication.

1.4.1 5G-TSN bridge

The standardization work to integrate 5G with TSN started in 3GPP Release 16. The 5G system is represented as a set of IEEE-compliant TSN bridges (also referred to as virtual 5G bridges). The 5G TSN bridge can be connected to TSN nodes (part of a TSN network) in a seamless way. The 5G network comprises a 5G core network and a Radio Access Network (RAN). A User Plane Function (UPF) of the 5G core network acts as a gateway towards the TSN network. The RAN can span over a larger geographic area, like a whole production plant, to provide wireless connectivity to one or more User Equipments (UEs).

Figure 1.2 5G-TSN integration

To interface the 5G system with the other TSN nodes, 3GPP introduced TSN translators (TT) at the Device side (DS-TT) and at the Network side (NW-TT), as shown in Figure 1.2. The translators provide TSN Ethernet interfaces and mimic the expected behavior of a number of TSN features, without the need to radically modify the functionalities of the 5G nodes and functions. To interface with the TSN Network Controller (i.e. Centralized Network Configuration controller, CNC), a TSN Application Function (TSN AF) was defined. The TSN AF obtains the 5G bridge capabilities and provides them to the CNC, while the CNC configures the 5G bridge via the TSN AF. The TSN AF translates the capabilities to the parameters that the CNC handles and translates the configuration from the CNC into a flow set up in the 5G system. Finally, the TSN AF also handles the time synchronization settings that can be configured by the CNC.

1.4.2 TSN scheduled traffic

Scheduled traffic is a feature of TSN that enables a strict time-schedule of every transmission. The CNC is in charge of generating a schedule for every TSN stream in the network and is responsible for configuring the transmission gates at every bridge egress port. At the egress port, the transmission gates for every egress queue can be open or closed. CNC calculates the Gate Control List (GCL) for every egress port in the network and configures every bridge accordingly. As can be seen in Figure 1.3, every egress port has multiple queues each handling one or more traffic classes (there are 8 traffic classes), a transmission selection algorithm and the transmission gate for every queue. The GCL has a set of commands indicating the intervals when the gates should be open or closed. This set of intervals repeats in a cyclic manner. The traffic in the queue will be transmitted when its gate is open and will be held when its gate is closed.

In the 5G TSN bridge the Scheduled Traffic is implemented at the DS-TT ports and NW-TT ports via a Hold and Forward buffering mechanism (H&F). H&F was defined for the purpose of implementing TSN. The H&F's current function is to hold frames of a queue when its gate state is closed, and forward frames from a queue when its transmission gate state is set to open. Other functionalities could be added to the H&F, such as a packet delay correction (PDC) method that is discussed in Section 2.

Figure 1.3 Bridge egress port and the Scheduled Traffic configuration (a.k.a. IEEE 802.1Qbv, or just Qbv), see [IEEE22-8021Q], Section 8.6.8.4.

1.5 Structure of the document

The second report on 6G centric enablers for dependable time-critical communications consists of five main sections. After the introduction, Section 2 delves into the comprehensive analysis of PDC methods and simulation-based evaluations. This is followed by a mathematical formulation for predictability and probabilistic latency prediction for wireless networks in Section 3. Architectural discussions related to learning and to observability are part of Section 4. RAN scheduling approaches are studied in Section 5. Finally, the conclusions of this report are presented in Section 6.

2 Packet delay correction

5G/6G exhibits a larger packet delay variation (PDV) compared to a regular wired Ethernet bridge. The measurements shown in Deliverable 3.1 [DET23-D31] show that the 5G system presents a PDV in the order of milliseconds, while the wired bridge shows a PDV in the order of 100s of nanoseconds. This issue makes time-sensitive delivery so difficult that cannot be easily handled by a TSN scheduler calculating an IEEE 802.1Qbv schedule for the TSN flows.

One major problem is the fact that this large jitter or PDV leads to an uncertain enqueueing and transmission order. As shown in Figure 2.1, a packet from Stream 1 (lilac) will normally be enqueueed before a packet from Stream 2 (orange). However, eventually and due to the large PDV, a packet from Stream 2 will be enqueueed before a packet from Stream 1 in the same egress queue for transmission. If many streams suffer from the same uncertainty belonging to the same traffic class, then some packets will miss their chance to get transmitted in the right order and will be delayed to the next cycle. This breaks the schedule because the effect propagates to the forthcoming cycles and will not maintain the desired delivery times.

Figure 2.1 IEEE 802.1Qbv scheduled traffic: uncertain enqueueing issue

Therefore, a solution is needed to remove PDV or compensate for it. By shrinking the PDV, in the range of microseconds rather than milliseconds, existing TSN wireless-unaware schedule algorithms can be applied without undesired packet disordering issue. In this section we focus on the PDV compensation applied within the 6G system (6GS) using packet delay correction (PDC) methods. PDC methods were defined and described in the deliverable D2.1 [DET23-D21]. In this deliverable we aim for a deeper analysis and evaluation of PDC methods.

2.1 PDC concept and analysis

PDC is a concept that aims at modifying the per-packet delay in order to obtain a low or zero level of PDV. To this purpose, PDCs usually rely on a hold and forward buffering mechanism at the traffic egress point to correct the delay experienced by a packet. By holding back the packets, the average delay increases. Hence PDC trades off with reduced PDV producing longer average delays. For most time-critical applications, high average latency is not as important as a low PDV, since it is sufficient that the packets arrive before their maximum delay bound.

2.1.1 Summary of PDC methods

As described in deliverable D2.1, we have defined the following PDC methods:

- 1) **Timestamp-based:** An ingress point (e.g., DS-TT or NW-TT) applies an ingress timestamp to packets belonging to the flow of interest (e.g., a TSN stream). This ingress timestamp travels with the packet as metadata to the egress point (e.g., NW-TT or DS-TT) where an egress timestamp is generated. The values of these two timestamps are used to calculate the residence time of the packet within the 6GS. Given a predefined maximum packet delay in the 6GS, PD_{max}, the packet is held at the egress point for “PD_{max} - residence time” and then forwarded to the next hop after removing the ingress timestamp from the packet. In this case, if all packets spend PD_{max}, then the PDV is zero. If instead of PD_{max}, a very small range of delay values is used, e.g., [PD_{min}, PD_{max}], then PDV becomes equal to this range. This solution requires time synchronization in both ingress and egress points.
- 2) **Virtual-timeslots-based:** This solution expands from the timestamp-based approach by using a predefined sequence number that states a new type of timestamp, namely the virtual timeslot. Instead of using an absolute time with high precision for the timestamping, the idea is to use a known timeslot size (i.e., not a single time value but a time range), whereby each timeslot is identified by an integer number. The ingress point inserts this integer value, and, like the timestamp based PDC, the egress port calculates the packet’s residence time based on the timeslot at which the packet arrived at the egress point. Then the egress point holds the packet for as many timeslots as the maximum predefined “TS_{max} - residence time”, before forwarding to the next hop. The benefit here is that the metadata size requires less bytes and fast hardware-speed timestamping is not required, which would imply a more costly interface at the ingress and egress points. This solution can provide a PDV that is in the order of the timeslot size.
- 3) **Re-transmission-based:** In this case the metadata in the packets will be the number of retransmissions for the data packet. The egress point, based on this information uses a Cyclic Queuing and Forwarding (CQF) system with an egress queue by considering the number of retransmissions. Packets are enqueued based on the retransmission number they carry as metadata, the actually served queue, and the CQF gate control list. The CQF that will cyclically select/serve the egress queue for transmission such that packets with larger number of retransmissions are transmitted earlier and packets with lower number of retransmissions are transmitted later, achieving that the lower delay bound is pushed towards the upper bound. In other words, all packets will approximately be delayed the same time as the packets with largest retransmission number. For more details, please refer to the deliverable D2.1 [DET23-D21]. The egress point in this case is placed after the air transmission and controls the lower bound of the packet delay distribution to become tighter toward the upper bound and thereby controlling the PDV introduced in the RAN segment which is caused by the Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) process.

Additionally, if the PDC requires to carry metadata such as the timestamp, virtual timeslot, or number of retransmissions, it is important to define how or where in the packet the metadata can be added. Solutions to transfer metadata have been presented in the deliverable D2.1, and are also discussed in Section 4.2.2.

2.1.2 PDC for periodic traffic

As can be noticed, the afore-discussed PDCs require some form of metadata in every packet (e.g., timestamp, number of retransmissions). In this section we propose a new PDC method specific for periodic traffic without any metadata in the packets. Indeed, if we analyze which type of traffic is most sensitive to PDV, then we will find that in most cases it is about periodic traffic. Packets have to arrive at a certain pace or period: not earlier and not later. This fact can be noted in Table 1 of the 5G-ACIA white paper on 5G integration with TSN [5GACIA21], where periodic traffic is either intolerant to PDV variations (or jitter) such as isochronous traffic, or has very low tolerance to PDV, such as cyclic-synchronous and cyclic-asynchronous traffic.

For example, due to the large PDV introduced today by the 5G TSN bridge, guarantees on periodic traffic delivery are difficult to achieve. In Figure 2.2, a packet being transmitted end-to-end hits a large uncertainty on its transmission time at the 5G TSN bridge. This leads to the fact that every packet in the flow will experience a different total delay. Periodic packets are sent one after the other separated by a periodicity time. If the packets experience a highly variable delay, then the delivery at the destination will not follow the said periodicity. In order to achieve a periodic delivery, a PDC is required such that packets show a near-to-zero PDV when passing through the 5G TSN bridge.

Figure 2.2 Effect of 5G PDV in periodic traffic

This new PDC for periodic traffic requires additional information. In particular, the value of the flow periodicity needs to be available at the egress point. The essence of this approach is to calculate the forwarding time of a packet n by simply adding the period value to the forwarding time (FT) of the previous packet ($n-1$) belonging to the same queue, as shown in Figure 2.3. The egress point keeps track of the last forwarding time, and if it knows the value of the flow period, then the egress point can also calculate the forwarding time of the next packet.

When it comes to the very first packet, it is forwarded at “packet arrival time at egress point + PD_max”, and then FT(0) is set with this value. With this we ensure that the successive packets will not catch up with the previous ones.

Figure 2.3 PDC method for periodic traffic and its application at the egress point (example DS-TT).
 $FT(n)$:forwarding time for packet n (for integer $n>0$)

This PDC presents an issue when a packet is lost or delayed at a previous hop (before reaching the 6G TSN bridge). Indeed, since the PDC is based on adding periodicity to the latest transmission time, if a packet is missed, then the whole mechanism would fail. An additional condition should be added to allow the continuity of the periodical delivery of further packet, as follows:

- The egress point detects when a packet has been lost by the time the next deadline is reached. In this case, the egress point will keep calculating the next forwarding time (even when there is no packet) until a packet arrives. When a packet arrives, it will be forwarded exactly at the latest forwarding time that was calculated.

2.1.3 PDC categorization

Different options of PDC can be categorized based on analysis of their applicability and limitations. A possible categorization can be discussed with regards to the PDC application dependency, PDC precision, PDC scope, and PDC overhead.

- PDC application dependency refers to the level at which the PDC can be applied to traffic. PDC can be applied for any type of traffic, or just to one type of traffic (e.g., periodic traffic).
- PDC precision is the level at which the PDV can be reduced. It relates to whether the PDC is able to achieve zero (or near zero) PDV, or some low PDV is reached, and what is the magnitude order of the resulting PDV (after applying PDC), e.g., μ s, ms. Another aspect to consider with precision is the associated cost or complexity to reach it.
- PDC scope indicates to which end points the PDC is applied to. As discussed in D2.1, PDC can be applied at DS-TT and NW-TT, i.e., at the edges of the 6GS. But it could as well be applied to a specific segment within the 6GS, for instance a PDC can be applied in the RAN segment, between Next Generation Node B (gNB) and UE.
- PDC overhead is added when certain metadata is required to be transported in the packet to which delay correction will be applied. The overhead also involves the means to transport the metadata.

Analyzing the categorization of PDCs based on the presented mechanisms so far, we can reach the following Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Analysis of different PDC mechanisms with respect to different characteristic categories

PDC	Application dependency	Precision	Scope	Overhead
Timestamp	No	Very precise (μs -level), but costly to implement at wire-speed.	End-to-end or within a particular segment in the 6G or 5G-Adv system.	Yes Every packet carries a “timestamp”. Transport via 3GPP protocol headers is possible (see deliverable D2.1) but requires standardization.
Virtual timeslots	No	Bounded. Precision varies depending on the size of the timeslot. The larger the timeslot, the larger the PDV; suitable precisions may be in the order of 10’s of μs , or 100 μs .	End-to-end or within a particular segment in the 6G or 5G-Adv system.	Yes Every packet carries a “virtual timeslot”. Transport via 3GPP protocol headers is possible (see deliverable D2.1) but requires standardization. Also, for Ethernet traffic, timeslot number can be carried in the R-Tag header field.
Number of retransmissions	No	Bounded. max PDV = time needed for a retransmission cycle over the air interface (up to few ms).	5G-Adv/6G RAN segment	Yes Every packet carries a “number of retransmission”. Transport via 3GPP protocol headers is possible (see deliverable D2.1) but requires standardization.
Periodicity	Yes, only for periodic traffic	Very precise (μs -level), also corrects any deviations in the periodicity introduced by previous hops.	End-to-end or within a particular segment in the 6G or 5G-Adv system.	No

Note that no assumption has been considered regarding maximum packet length, so further study will be required to analyze the implications of fragmented packets.

2.1.4 Key takeaways

PDC can be very useful to compensate for the relatively large PDV that a 5G/6G system generates compared to regular wired bridges. Different methods have been proposed and each with their strengths and weaknesses in terms of precision, its dependency with the type of traffic, the scope of application, and overhead generated by PDC metadata carried in every packet. The choice of the PDC to be implemented in the 5G/6G system needs to be matched with the E2E traffic requirements.

2.2 PDC E2E evaluations

In the following, we evaluate the impact of PDC on IEEE 802.1Qbv scheduling. We consider two types of PDC: timestamp-based and virtual-timeslot-based.

We consider the scenario shown in Figure 2.4, where an automated guided vehicle (AGV) is connected to the backbone TSN network of a factory. The 6G TSN bridge is connecting two wired TSN network segments: the AGV-internal network and the TSN backbone. Using the 6GDetCom [DET23-D41] extension for the OMNeT++/INET framework, we simulate wireless packet delays as measured in a real 5G system [DET23-D41] and implementing PDC as a 6G capability. Throughout our experiments, a single Qbv queue per egress port was considered to amplify the bottleneck of compensating 6G PDV in TSN.

Figure 2.4 Simulation scenario

2.2.1 Effect of PDC in wireless-unaware Qbv scheduled traffic

Figure 2.5 End-to-end latency probability distribution for Best Effort traffic, and for Qbv traffic with and without PDC

First, we consider a scenario with 90 TSN streams, consisting of 50 wired streams that reside within the AGV-internal network or the TSN backbone, and 40 wireless streams (either in uplink or downlink direction). We evaluate the effects of PDC on a single wireless (uplink) stream F with a period/latency of 20 ms, a frame size of 100B, and a zero-jitter requirement.

The simulated end-to-end latencies of F are shown in Figure 2.5. We compare:

- *BestEffort (Baseline)*: Neither PDC nor IEEE 802.1Qbv is employed.
- *QbvWithoutPDC*: The IEEE 802.1Qbv gating mechanism is deployed without PDC.
- *QbvWithPDC*: The IEEE 802.1Qbv gating mechanism is deployed with PDC.

To compute the IEEE 802.1Qbv's Gate Control Lists (GCLs), the worst-case 6G packet delays are used for uplink/downlink TSN streams. Moreover, we employ the same GCLs for *QbvWithoutPDC* and *QbvWithPDC*. To retrieve meaningful results, the simulation is run for a total of 100k hypercycles.

Figure 2.5 captures the end-to-end latency and its variation in the form of violin plots. In the case of *BestEffort*, this representation clearly shows that the end-to-end latency of F is very similar to the

underlying 6G uplink packet delay distribution. Most notably, with a probability of approx. 99%, the latency of F lies within $[5ms, 10ms]$, whereas outliers can induce a latency of approx. 14 ms. For applications that are jitter-intolerant, this is clearly unacceptable. In contrast, *QbvWithoutPDC* shows a scheduling attempt that simply considers the worst-case delay for each transmission hop; an approach that is commonly employed in wired Time-Sensitive Networks. Contrary to the intended outcome, however, Figure 2.5 shows that the resulting latency of F can lie far beyond the acceptable deadline. This is caused by the fact that solely considering the worst-case delay does not sufficiently account for the 6G PDV. As a result, there can be unintended frame reordering within the egress queues, which causes frames to miss their transmission slots and can even push frames in the subsequent hypercycle. Indeed, by fully compensating the 6G PDV, *QbvWithPDC* can resolve this complication to deliver frames of F with zero-jitter before its deadline.

Further insights

While the above figure shows the experienced latency for a single stream, the effects of unintended frame reordering can be best seen from a global view on the complete set of streams. Figure 2.6 therefore provides a global view on the behavior of *QbvWithoutPDC* by showing the experienced end-to-end latencies for each TSN stream in the network (for the first 10 s of the simulation). Again, the underlying problem is rooted in the 6G PDV that, compared to delay variations in wired networks, lie within the range of milliseconds. For wireless-unaware schedulers that neglect this difference, this can cause two frames f_1 and f_2 (of different uplink TSN streams) to be enqueued at the NW-TT in the order $f_1 < f_2$ or $f_2 < f_1$. Figure 2.6 shows that this effect does not stay isolated to the individual streams of f_1 and f_2 , but that it can spread throughout the entire network and nullify any QoS guarantee.

Figure 2.6 Relative arrival time for wireless-unaware Qbv schedule and without PDC

In comparison, PDC enables the deployment of conventional (wireless-unaware) scheduling techniques that do not have to pay special attention to significant 6G PDV. In particular, Figure 2.7 shows the resulting transmission ordering. It can be seen that each frame is delivered at its listener before the deadline of 20 ms and with zero PDV.

Figure 2.7 Relative arrival time for wireless-unaware Qbv schedule and with PDC

2.2.2 Impact of virtual time slots

In the previous section, we considered perfect timestamping for PDC. To show the impact of using virtual timeslots at different levels of granularity, we are mainly interested in their final effects on scheduling in IEEE 802.1Qbv. Using the same network topology and wired streams as before, we therefore evaluate the maximum number of wireless streams for which a feasible schedule is found. The experiments are performed for different virtual time slot sizes ($1\mu s - 500\mu s$).

Figure 2.8. Effects of the virtual timeslot granularity on schedulability

Looking at the results shown in Figure 2.8, the virtual timeslot granularity has a clear effect on the number of wireless streams that can be scheduled. In particular, the virtual timeslot size essentially introduces a form of PDV that has to be de-jittered in the TSN queues at the egress side of the 6G TSN

bridge. Considering the maximum downlink packet delay of the utilized measurements is approx. 17 ms [DET23-D41], a granularity of 500 μ s and a hypercycle of 20 ms solely allows

$$\frac{20ms - 17ms}{500\mu s} = 6$$

frames per egress queue without overflowing to the subsequent hypercycle. In contrast, Figure 2.8 shows that this de-jittering time is not the main bottleneck for a virtual slot size of up to 10 μ s.

2.2.3 Key takeaways

With these evaluations it was shown that Qbv scheduled traffic will perform very poorly when any (virtual) node introduces significant PDV: streams' deadlines cannot be fulfilled. The reason is that the TSN scheduler considers the worst case 6G-delay in order to make its per-node scheduling calculations. It was noted that large PDV can lead to uncertain enqueueing where packets from different TSN streams are enqueued in an unexpected order (as per TSN scheduler calculations). This leads to a number of packets, that should have been enqueued earlier than other packets, to be postponed for the next Qbv hypercycle and consequently missing their deadline. On the other hand, when Qbv scheduled traffic is used in conjunction with a PDC method such as the timestamp-based PDC, then the delivery is just as expected and on-time since there is no overflow of packets to subsequent Qbv hypercycles. Additionally virtual-timeslot-based PDC is evaluated, and its impact is reflected in a reduced number of streams that can be scheduled without incurring in the issue of uncertain enqueueing.

3 Data-driven latency prediction

In this section we propose a mathematical definition for predictability – the ability to anticipate future QoS KPIs for dependable and time-critical communications. Furthermore, we discuss a probabilistic delay prediction for wireless systems.

3.1 Predictability framework

The stringent requirements of the majority of the 6G use cases ask for proactive network adaptation approaches via predicting QoS KPIs such as end-to-end delay in advance. Proactive adaptation can offer major gains to the operation of these applications. For instance, predicting in advance a potential increase in the network delay and/or deterioration of computing resources will enable the network and/or the respective application to adapt and achieve the required QoS [MGZ20], [BMK+22], [KMP+21], [TDJ+23].

Consequently, there is a current notion in the community on utilizing end-to-end delay probability predictors, especially in the integration with TSN [DET23-D21] [DET23-D31]. Moreover, the 5G Automotive Association (5GAA) has introduced the concept of predictive QoS, which refers to the mechanisms enabling mobile networks to provide notifications about predicted QoS changes to interested consumers in advance [5GAA20]. ETSI, in the context of Mobile Edge Computing (MEC), has also introduced the notion of predictive QoS support [ETSI18]. In this context, the prediction of potential handovers leading to the estimated QoS performance is described as the key solution for mitigating any service interruption and supporting the application requirements.

Predictability in this context refers to the ability to anticipate the future performance of the system based on current and historical data. As the communication system interacts with the environment, the predictability of the system extends beyond just the immediate network parameters. If the environmental conditions—such as interference patterns, user mobility, or traffic loads—exhibit non-random behavior and can be forecasted with reasonable accuracy, this adds a new dimension to the system’s overall predictability. Therefore, it is essential to understand how a communication system can be considered predictable, and to identify the factors that enhance or undermine this predictability.

Inspired by the above questions, in this work, a mathematical definition of predictability is proposed that is based on information theory concepts and a probabilistic forecasting setup. We introduce this definition and examine its consequences within a multihop communication system model where the conditions are governed by a Markov chain. We study both exact and approximate derivations of predictability within these abstract systems, such as a queueing system, for end-to-end delay prediction. Queuing systems can effectively model large-scale effects in communication networks.

3.1.1 Background and related works

Researchers have developed various measures to assess the predictability of complex dynamic systems, all of which focus on predicting specific single or multi-dimensional critical metrics. These works can be categorized based on the following criteria: the comprehensiveness of the predictability definition, whether they analyze only the target metric or incorporate side information, and whether predictability is derived empirically or through a model-driven approach.

At the most basic level, there are works that define predictability in a setup where point prediction of a univariate metric is desired. Autocorrelation, which evaluates how well a time series correlates with its own time-lagged versions, is a widely used indicator of predictability in finance [LLK13]. Permutation entropy (PE) is the metric employed in fields like ecology and physics, to gauge predictability [BP02], [GJB14], [PIG+19]. PE measures time series complexity by quantifying the diversity and frequency of ordinal patterns formed by subsequences of the series. A higher permutation entropy indicates more diverse motifs, leading to lower predictability. This indicator is mostly empirically evaluated and has been applied to various domains, including predicting infectious disease outbreaks [SP19], and ecological systems [PIG+19]. Abeliuk et al. explore the relationship between predictability and sampling in partially observed systems. They evaluate multiple predictability measures such as PE and autocorrelation in outbreaks of infectious diseases, digital forum interactions, and software development projects [AHF+20].

Besides autocorrelation and PE, another common approach in defining predictability is to find the lower bound on prediction error [Ber96]. In some works, the empirically determined entropy of the target metric is incorporated in Fano’s inequality to derive the bound on error. Using this approach Li et al. investigate the limits of predictability for urban vehicular location and staying time [LJH+14]. More information-theoretic measures of predictability have inspired numerous studies. For instance, studies on the predictability of human mobility and conversation use random entropy, uncorrelated entropy, and conditional entropy to measure predictability [SQB+10], [TNS+11].

More advanced studies in this category incorporate side information or covariates into the predictability model. As a result, the selected predictability measure is typically relative entropy, conditional entropy, or mutual information between the side information and the target metric. Bialek et al. define predictive information as the mutual information between past and future states of a

time series as a criterion for predictability [BNT01]. Haven et al. used a Gaussian ensemble prediction to assess relative entropy for predictability analysis [HMA05]. More recently, Li et al. applied conditional entropy to traffic forecasting, highlighting the limitations of traffic predictability [LKL22]. Also, Fang and Lee explore predictability in the context of regression problems in machine learning. They analyze predictability in this context using the conditional entropy between the features and the label and introduce lower and upper bounds for it [FL24]. Due to the incorporation of side information, these predictability analyses are considered more comprehensive from our perspective.

In atmospheric sciences literature, where the probabilistic forecasting of the weather systems is of interest, the information-theoretic definition of predictability with side information is gaining more attention [Del04], [Kri19]. In a series of papers, DelSole et al. define predictability as the difference between forecast and climatological distributions (marginal distribution), with the latter serving as the baseline for probabilistic information about the metric where no side information is incorporated. Various information theory measures were proposed and analyzed to quantify predictability in systems with linear stochastic models and Gaussian processes [DT07]. Among the works that are related to networking and communication systems, Ding et al. examine the predictability of radio spectrum state dynamics using Fano's inequality. Their findings show high predictability in real-world spectrum measurements, which has significant implications for cognitive radio networks and 5G spectrum sharing [DWW+15]. In another paper, Sang and Li apply predictability analysis to an abstract network model with a queue. They investigate the predictability of network traffic by analyzing how far into the future traffic rates can be predicted with a given error constraint on the prediction problem [SL00].

Despite the growing focus on quality-of-service prediction in stochastic communication systems, comprehensive predictability analyses are both necessary and, to the best of our knowledge, largely nonexistent. This work addresses this gap by adopting a thorough predictability model and demonstrating its implications for communication system performance. Drawing inspiration from the predictability framework used in atmospheric science, which is an information-theoretic measure well-suited for probabilistic forecasting, our definition compares the conditional distribution of performance given the side information or observations with its marginal distribution. Such a definition offers great capabilities not only in applying it to various dynamical systems, but also we show how it can model imperfect observability. Moreover, since Markov chains are widely used in queue modeling and various fields—including stochastic processes and machine learning—due to their effectiveness in modeling dynamic systems with memoryless state transitions, we employ the Markovian assumption for the system's dynamics. In the following section we step into system model and predictability definition in more detail.

3.1.2 System model and problem formulation

Forecasting performance in a communication network becomes more manageable and precise by breaking down the system into independent modules and modeling each individually. This also allows for more efficient proactive adjustments, as we can more accurately pinpoint the sources of performance variations or declines [MTS+24]. These components can correspond to tandem data transmission links or, within a single link, to multiple processes that sequentially handle data bits to ensure reliable and efficient communication. Furthermore, the condition or state of each subsystem can be monitored and, according to domain knowledge, correlated with performance.

We consider a communication system that consists of M independent subsystems or hops as shown in Figure 3.1. In time slot n (time is slotted), subsystem m exhibits a performance measure denoted by $Z_n^{(m)}$ which is a random variable over the discrete space \mathcal{Z} , for example, packet delay. $\Pr(Z_n^{(m)})$ denotes the marginal distribution (or prior distribution) and is considered stationary. It constitutes a baseline for the information content about performance, disregarding all state observations. This distribution can be obtained by random sampling of the performance. In case of end-to-end delay (without packet drops) total performance is obtained via $Z_n = \sum_{m=1}^M Z_n^{(m)}$.

Figure 3.1 Multi-hop communication system model with observable measures being conditions and performance

Moreover, each subsystem has an internal state or condition measure denoted by $X_n^{(m)}$ that influences performance, for example, the congestion level in the subsystem. Conditions are defined over a discrete finite state space $\mathcal{X}^{(m)}$ of size $K^{(m)}$. Then, the collection of all the state variables belonging to each subsystem is denoted by $X_n = \{X_n^{(1)}, \dots, X_n^{(m)}, \dots, X_n^{(M)}\}$ with size K . Observations of state measures across the system collected up to time n are denoted by $O_{0:n}$. Depending on the scenario, observations can include all parts, or an imperfect version of the conditions.

We consider three different observability defects in our model: first, delayed observations, which is particularly crucial when a network of remote nodes is involved in the packet route. In this scenario, monitoring information would arrive with a delay to the prediction and adaptation point, i.e., $O_n = X_{n-d}$. In the second case, we may choose to ignore certain subsystems and not observe their state, i.e., $O_n \subset X_n$ due to the overhead that the monitoring task introduces. The third case, which also concerns overhead, mandates aggregated states. In this scenario, we assume states of \mathcal{X} are aggregated to \mathcal{A} , i.e., there exists a surjective map $\phi: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ with $|\mathcal{A}| \leq |\mathcal{X}|$ (or $\bar{K} \leq K$ as $|\mathcal{A}| = \bar{K}$). Then, the observations are conducted on the aggregated states $O_n = \phi(X_n)$.

The distribution of performance right after observations become available denoted by $\Pr(Z_n | O_{0:n})$ is the posterior distribution. The marginal distribution is related to the posterior distribution by the chain rule as it is obtained by integrating out all observations:

$$\Pr(Z_n) = \sum_{o_{0:n}} \Pr(Z_n | O_{0:n} = o_{0:n}) \Pr(O_{0:n} = o_{0:n}) \quad (1)$$

The primary objective of any performance predictor in this setting is to capture the relationship between the observations and future performance. The probability distribution of the performance metric L timeslots into the future, based on the observations collected up to the present moment, is the forecast distribution:

$$\Pr(Z_{n+L} \mid O_{0:n} = o_{0:n}) \quad (2)$$

We examine performance in communication systems whose conditions adhere to the Markovian property, which is applicable in numerous contexts and mathematically manageable. We define two sets of conditional independence assumptions on the system: first, Z_n is independent of all other condition states except the current one X_n , and second, X_n is independent of X_1, \dots, X_{n-2} given X_{n-1} (the first-order Markov property), i.e.,

$$\Pr(Z_n \mid Z_{0:n-1}, X_{0:n}) = \Pr(Z_n \mid X_n) \quad (3)$$

A third assumption for the remainder of this work is that the simplified posterior distribution mentioned above is stationary, meaning that

$$\forall L, \Pr(Z_{n+L} \mid X_{n+L}) = \Pr(Z_n \mid X_n) \quad (4)$$

For ease of notation, we represent the Probability Mass Function (PMF) of this distribution as $\Pr(Z_n = z \mid X_n = x) = r_x(z)$, where $z \in \mathcal{Z}$ and $x \in \mathcal{X}$.

Figure 3.2 Dependencies in the performance model.

As shown in Figure 3.2, this system forms an Observable Markov Model (OMM) where the sequence $\{X_0, X_1, \dots, X_n\}$ is a discrete-time, time-homogeneous Markov chain with finite state space \mathcal{X} . The transition probability from state x to state y is denoted by $P(x, y) = \Pr(X_{n+1} = y \mid X_n = x)$ which forms the transition probability matrix P . L step state transition probability is derived via $P^L(x, y)$. Moreover, we assume that X is an irreducible and aperiodic Markov chain, therefore it has a stationary distribution π that state probabilities converge to for large lead times. Then, for all x, y we have $P^L(x, y) \rightarrow \pi(y)$ as $L \rightarrow \infty$. Also, we assume the chain is reversible, which is an assumption satisfied by all random walks on undirected graphs, as well as many other Markov chains such as queues:

$$\forall (x, y) \in \mathcal{X}^2, \pi(x)P(x, y) = \pi(y)P(y, x) \quad (5)$$

Reversibility allows applying spectral analysis on the speed of convergence that we use later on. In reversible chains, the spectral theorem guarantees that P admits $K = |\mathcal{X}|$ real eigenvalues, which can be ordered as

$$1 = \lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_K > -1 \quad (6)$$

and there is an orthonormal basis of real-valued eigenfunctions $(f_j)_{j \leq K}$ corresponding to these eigenvalues with respect to the inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_\pi$ [Win03]. Closed-form solutions for eigenvalues

and eigenfunctions exist for numerous basic and well-organized Markov chain models, including random walks on circular structures, multi-dimensional cubes, and various graph types.

In this work we examine more specialized Markov chains, particularly the Geo/Geo/1/K queue, which represents the discrete-time counterpart of the M/M/1/K queue. In this case, the packets arrive according to a Bernoulli process and the probability of arriving during a time slot is $\lambda = 1 - \bar{\lambda}$. Service times are geometrically distributed, and the probability of completion of a service during a slot is $\mu = 1 - \bar{\mu}$. The utilization factor is denoted by $\rho = \lambda/\mu$. The performance metric Z_n will be the sojourn time of the queue, and the queue size will be the measurable state of the system X_n . As the number of states in our analysis should be finite, we consider the maximum length of K for the queue.

To formulate predictability in general, we rely on the forecast and the marginal distributions. An event is considered unpredictable not because its distribution is entirely unknown, but because the forecast distribution does not significantly differ from the marginal distribution. Based on that, we define predictability in the following definition.

Definition 1: A system is unpredictable if the forecast and marginal distributions do not differ if:

$$Pr(Z_{n+L} | O_{0:n} = o_{0:n}) = Pr(Z_{n+L}) \quad (7)$$

According to this definition, the loss of predictability occurs when the future state Z_{n+L} is statistically independent of the observations. Equivalently, we define the degree of predictability as Total Variation (TV) distance between the forecast and marginal distributions

$$D_n(L) = \|Pr(Z_{n+L} | O_{0:n} = o_{0:n}) - Pr(Z_{n+L})\|_{TV} \quad (8)$$

where the TV distance is a statistical metric distance defined by

$$TV(p, q) := \sup_{B \subset Z} |p(B) - q(B)| \quad (9)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{z \in Z} |p(z) - q(z)| \quad (10)$$

for probability mass functions p and q .

Total Variation distance is a metric that ranges between zero and one and benefits from numerous properties for bounding and approximation. Intuitively, the system is unpredictable when the TV distance between the forecast and the marginal is very small, so the performance and observations are almost independent. On the contrary, the system is predictable when TV is close to 1 since the distributions are very different, and that means the observations make a difference in our prediction of the performance. This framework implies that predictability is a combined property of the dynamical system and the observations. The observations might be irrelevant, leading to zero predictability, or the system conditions might change in a completely random manner, rendering the incorporation of the observations ineffective.

It is important to acknowledge that the predictability framework introduced in this work may not be universally applicable to all systems. Specifically, it might seem counterintuitive when applied to deterministic or nearly deterministic processes that do not need side information. For example, a

process that always takes the value 1 would be considered unpredictable according to this definition because the forecast and marginal distributions are identical, yielding a Total Variation distance of zero. However, in such a scenario, alternative measures like entropy could be more appropriate, as they would correctly identify the process as fully predictable due to its zero entropy. Thus, the proposed definition is particularly well-suited for systems where the primary concern is the utility of observations in reducing uncertainty. This is especially relevant for networked systems where the decision to incorporate additional signals in performance prediction must be weighed against the cost of processing and routing them.

Definition 2: Epsilon-predictable horizon of a system is defined by the maximum lead time that predictability remains greater than ϵ :

$$H_\epsilon = \max\{L, \forall n: D_n(L) \geq \epsilon\} \quad (11)$$

This metric guarantees that if we have observations up to time n , then we will have informative forecasts up to time $n + L$, since the forecast distribution will always have minimum distance ϵ with the marginal distribution. Essentially, it reflects how quickly the observations lose their importance, as the system evolves quickly to its stationary state. Therefore, epsilon-predictable horizon can be essential in analyzing predictability of complex dynamic systems.

In addressing the problems considered in this study, we begin by assessing the predictability of system models under conditions of imperfect observations. Specifically, we aim to determine the predictability of the systems with the following forecast distributions:

- with delayed observation

$$\Pr(Z_{n+L} \mid O_n = X_{n-d}) \quad (12)$$

- with the observation of aggregated states

$$\Pr(Z_{n+L} \mid O_n = \phi(X_n)) \quad (13)$$

- and with partial observation in multi-hop cases

$$\Pr(Z_{n+L} \mid O_n \subset \{X_n^{(1)}, \dots, X_n^{(M)}\}) \quad (14)$$

Next, we will determine upper bounds on predictability based on L for both single-hop and multi-hop system models, which can then be converted to an upper limit on H_ϵ . Finally, we will derive exact and approximation solutions for the predictability of sojourn time in basic queuing systems, specifically Geo/Geo/1/K.

We will evaluate the results in both single-hop and multi-hop scenarios under various configurations with imperfect observations and state aggregation. Building on the system model and predictability definitions established in this section, we now delve into a detailed predictability analysis for Markov-modulated systems in the following section.

3.1.3 Predictability analysis

To begin, we consider perfect observation of conditions, as $O_n = X_n$ for all n , until otherwise specified. In the following lemma, we introduce two immediate conclusions which apply to any Markov-modulated probabilistic performance measure.

Lemma 1: In a system where the performance Z_n is related to Markov chain conditions X_n via a known stationary posterior distribution $\Pr(Z_n | X_n)$, forecast distribution (distribution of performance L time slots ahead, given the observed state x) can be derived as

$$\Pr(Z_{n+L} | X_n = x) = \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} P^L(x, y) \Pr(Z_n | X_n = y) \quad (15)$$

Marginal distribution of performance can be obtained via

$$\Pr(Z_{n+L}) = \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} \pi(y) \Pr(Z_n | X_n = y) \quad (16)$$

Proof: we begin by expanding forecast definition using law of total probability as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(Z_{n+L} = z | X_n = x) &= \\ \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} \Pr(Z_{n+L} = z | X_{n+L} = y, X_n = x) \Pr(X_{n+L} = y | X_n = x) & \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Then, according to first-order Markov property:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(Z_{n+L} = z | X_n = x) &= \\ \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} \Pr(Z_{n+L} = z | X_{n+L} = y) \Pr(X_{n+L} = y | X_n = x) & \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

The definition of Markov chain's transition matrix lets us simplify more:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(Z_{n+L} = z | X_n = x) &= \\ \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} \Pr(Z_{n+L} = z | X_{n+L} = y) P^L(x, y) &= \\ \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} r_y(z) P^L(x, y) & \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

For the marginal distribution, again we expand it using law of total probability as

$$\Pr(Z_{n+L} = z) = \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} \Pr(Z_{n+L} = z | X_{n+L} = y) \Pr(X_{n+L} = y) \quad (20)$$

Moreover, we use the definition of Markov chain's stationary state probabilities to finish the proof

$$\Pr(Z_{n+L} = z) = \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} \Pr(Z_{n+L} = z | X_{n+L} = y) \pi(y) \quad (21)$$

$$= \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} r_y(z) \pi(y)$$

This lemma indicates that in such a system, the forecast distribution becomes a mixture model with kernels defined by the posterior distribution and weights defined by Markov chain's transient state probabilities. As for the marginal distribution, regardless of the observations, it also becomes a mixture model with the same kernels, but weights are defined by the Markov chain's stationary state probabilities.

Theorem 1: Predictability of a Markov-modulated process Z_n with Markov chain probabilities P , π and posterior distributions $r_y(z)$, based on the perfect observation of the state x is characterized as follows:

$$D_n(L) = \sup_{A \subset \mathcal{Z}} \left| \sum_{z \in A} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} (P^L(x, y) - \pi(y)) r_y(z) \right| \quad (22)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \left| \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} (P^L(x, y) - \pi(y)) r_y(z) \right| \quad (23)$$

In the following subsections, we address more specific scenarios with imperfect observations, spectral analysis, multi-hop, and queueing systems.

Imperfect observations impact

We analyze the impact of imperfect observations on predictability in two parts:

a) **Delayed Observations:** This scenario is particularly critical given a network of remote nodes is involved. Observations must be transmitted to the forecast location, introducing potential delays where $O_n = X_{n-d}$.

Lemma 2: The predictability of a Markov-modulated process for the lead time L given observations delayed by d timeslots equals the predictability of the system with perfect observations but for the lead time $L + d$.

When the observation delay increases, it eventually exceeds the epsilon-predictable horizon, and the forecast converges to the marginal distribution, rendering the observation ineffective. Therefore, the delay in the observations must be smaller than the epsilon-predictable horizon of the system to have useful predictions.

b) **Aggregated States Observation:** In this scenario, the aggregation results in a new Markov chain with probabilities \bar{P} , $\bar{\pi}$ and a new posterior distribution $\bar{r}_a(z)$ for any $a \in \mathcal{A}$. Since Lemma 1 and Theorem 1 would hold true for this new aggregated setup, we can derive predictability accordingly. In the following lemma, we demonstrate how to construct \bar{P} , $\bar{\pi}$, and $\bar{r}_a(z)$.

Lemma 3: Suppose the states of a Markov chain \mathcal{X} are aggregated via the surjective map ϕ resulting in a new Markov chain with state space \mathcal{A} and probabilities $\bar{P}, \bar{\pi}$. The aggregate transition matrix denoted by \bar{P} is derived by

$$\bar{P}(a, b) = \frac{\sum_{x \in \phi^{-1}(a)} \sum_{y \in \phi^{-1}(b)} P(x, y) \pi(x)}{\pi(\phi^{-1}(a))} \quad (24)$$

The posterior distribution is obtained via

$$\bar{r}_a(z) = \frac{\sum_{y \in \phi^{-1}(a)} \pi(y) r_y(z)}{\pi(\phi^{-1}(a))} \quad (25)$$

The aggregate stationary distribution is evident to be

$$\bar{\pi}(b) = \pi(\phi^{-1}(b)) \quad (26)$$

In the next section we opt for a more intuitive and robust understanding of predictability by analyzing the inherent properties of the Markov chain with spectral analysis, rather than solely relying on the estimation/assumption of state transition probabilities.

Markov chain spectral properties impact

In the following lemma, we summarize the literature on spectral analysis which is applicable on the Total Variation distance to equilibrium in reversible Markov chains.

Lemma 4 ([Win03], [Sou20]): In a reversible Markov chain, for any starting state x , the Total Variation distance to stationary state probabilities is bounded as

$$\|P^L(x, \cdot) - \pi\|_{\text{TV}} \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{j=2}^K \lambda_j^{2L} f_j^2(x) \right)^{1/2} \quad (27)$$

Suppose $\lambda_* = \max\{|\lambda|, \lambda \neq 1\}$, then $\xi = 1 - \lambda_*$ denotes the spectral gap which can simplify the bound further:

$$\|P^L(x, \cdot) - \pi\|_{\text{TV}} \leq \frac{1}{2} \lambda_*^L \left(\frac{1}{\pi(x)} - 1 \right)^{1/2} \quad (28)$$

Spectral gap is known to provide a crucial measure on the rate at which the chain converges to its stationary distribution. This measure quantifies the chain's mixing properties: a larger spectral gap implies faster convergence, meaning that the distribution of the chain's states will quickly approach the stationary distribution.

By employing the spectral analysis principles, we derive an upper bound on the predictability of general Markovian systems, which is introduced in the following theorem.

Theorem 2 (Spectral-Based Predictability Bound): Predictability of a Markov-modulated process Z_n with Markov chain probabilities P, π and stationary posterior distribution $r_y(z)$, based on the perfect observation of the state x is upper bounded as follows:

$$D_n(L) \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{j=2}^K \lambda_j^{2L} f_j^2(x) \right)^{1/2} \sqrt{2}(R-1)^{1/2} \quad (29)$$

Where

$$R = \sum_z \frac{\sum_y \pi(y) r_y^2(z)}{\sum_y \pi(y) r_y(z)}, \text{ and } 1 \leq R \leq K \quad (30)$$

The inequality can be further simplified using the second largest eigenvalue as

$$D_n(L) \leq \frac{1}{2} \lambda_*^L \left(\frac{1}{\pi(x)} - 1 \right)^{1/2} \sqrt{2}(R-1)^{1/2} \quad (31)$$

This theorem suggests that the predictability upper bound decays geometrically, with the same rate that the Markov chain converges to stationarity. Upper bounds in Equations 31 and 28 are different in only one term which is sensitive to the closeness of posterior distributions $r_y(z)$. The minimum value of R , i.e. 1, occurs when all conditional distributions are similar and makes the predictability zero as was expected. On the other hand, we get the maximum, i.e. $K = |\mathcal{X}|$, when conditional distributions have minimal overlap.

Remark 1: For the cases that $\frac{3}{2} < R \leq K$, a tighter upper bound on the predictability is the Markov chain's Total Variation distance to equilibrium.

Proof: using triangle inequality and $0 \leq r_y(z) \leq 1 \forall y \in \mathcal{X}, \forall z \in \mathcal{Z}$ on Theorem 1 we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_n(L) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \left| \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} (P^L(x, y) - \pi(y)) r_y(z) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} (|P^L(x, y) - \pi(y)| r_y(z)) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} |P^L(x, y) - \pi(y)| \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} r_y(z) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{X}} |P^L(x, y) - \pi(y)| = \frac{1}{2} \|P^L(x, \cdot) - \pi\|_{\text{TV}} \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Theorem 2 introduces a novel approach to analyzing observable Markov models that modulate a secondary process through a known, stationary posterior distribution. Unlike traditional Markov chain mixing time analyses that focus on the Total Variation distance between stationary and transient state probabilities, our work provides an upper bound on the Total Variation distance between the secondary processes modulated by these different state probabilities. This advancement offers a new perspective on the convergence behavior of complex, multi-layered stochastic systems.

The subsequent section explores techniques for analyzing predictability in multi-hop systems.

Predictability in multi-hop systems

End-to-end performance predictability analysis in a multi-hop system as shown in Figure 3.1 requires an assumption on the performance measure and how it is obtained in total. In scenarios involving multiple hops, we consider Z_n to represent the end-to-end delay. Due to the summation, the total delay distribution will be the convolution of each hop's delay distribution both for forecasts and marginals as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(Z_{n+L} | X_n = x) = \\ \Pr(Z_{n+L}^{(1)} | X_n^{(1)} = x^{(1)}) * \Pr(Z_{n+L}^{(2)} | X_n^{(2)} = x^{(2)}) * \\ \dots * \Pr(Z_{n+L}^{(M)} | X_n^{(M)} = x^{(M)}), \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

$$\Pr(Z_{n+L}) = \Pr(Z_{n+L}^{(1)}) * \Pr(Z_{n+L}^{(2)}) * \dots * \Pr(Z_{n+L}^{(M)}) \quad (34)$$

where for each hop, marginal and forecast distributions can be derived via Lemma 1.

Obtaining predictability using the above method becomes less tractable as the dimensions of the system grow. In this context, identifying approximation or bounding techniques applicable to the problem is helpful. Below we propose a key lemma regarding the predictability in tandem systems where the end-to-end delay is subject to forecast.

Lemma 5 (Subadditivity of Predictability): The predictability of a tandem multi-hop system, assuming independence of the hops, is upper-bounded via the sum of predictability of each hop as

$$D_n(L) \leq \sum_{m=1}^M D_n^{(m)}(L) \quad (35)$$

This lemma proves beneficial especially when examining the predictability of a multi-hop system with incomplete observability i.e. $O_n \subset X_n$. In deriving the bound by adding the predictability across all hops, if the state in one or more hops is unobserved, their predictability drops to zero and does not affect the summation in Equation 35. We will investigate this in the next section in more detail.

Next, we opt to apply the predictability analysis to Geo/Geo/1 queue, which is the discrete time analogue of the M/M/1 queue.

Geo/Geo/1/K queue predictability

In this subsection, we utilize the previously mentioned predictability concepts and methods to the Geo/Geo/1/K queue model. The target metric Z_n for this forecast system is the sojourn time of the queue. The transition matrix in this queue is given by

$$\Pr(X_n = j | X_{n-1} = i) = \begin{cases} \lambda\bar{\mu} & \text{if } j = i + 1, 0 \leq i \leq K - 1 \\ \mu\bar{\lambda} & \text{if } j = i - 1, 1 \leq i \leq K \\ 1 - \lambda\bar{\mu} & \text{if } j = i = 0 \\ \lambda\mu + \bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu} & \text{if } j = i, 1 \leq i \leq K - 1 \\ 1 - \mu\bar{\lambda} & \text{if } j = i = K \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

and the corresponding Markov chain is depicted in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 Geo/Geo/1/K Markov chain states and transition probabilities.

In the following theorem we describe an exact derivation of predictability for this queuing model based on the observation of queue length and Theorem 1.

Theorem 3: The predictability of delay in a Geo/Geo/1/K queue given the observation of the system size denoted by x is described as follows:

$$D_n(L) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_z \left[\sum_{y=1}^K \frac{2}{K+1} \beta^{\frac{y-x}{2}} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\alpha_k^L}{\left[1 - 2\sqrt{\beta} \cos\left(\frac{k\pi}{K+1}\right) + \beta\right]} \left[\sin\left(\frac{xk\pi}{K+1}\right) - \sqrt{\beta} \sin\left(\frac{(x+1)k\pi}{K+1}\right) \right] \right] NB(z; y, \mu) \quad (37)$$

, where $\alpha_k = \lambda\mu + \bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu} + 2\sqrt{\lambda\mu\bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu}} \cos\left(\frac{k\pi}{K+1}\right)$ and $\beta = \frac{\lambda\bar{\mu}}{\mu\bar{\lambda}}$.

We propose an alternative approach to the method for two reasons. Firstly, because of the possible computational demands, and secondly, because of the difficulty in determining the relationship between model parameters and predictability. Hence, we present this approximation in the next proposition.

Proposition 1: The predictability of the sojourn time of a Geo/Geo/1/K queue with a very large K for L time slots in future based on the observation of the queue size x is approximated as

$$D_n(L) \approx \frac{\beta^{\frac{1-x}{2}}}{\pi} (1 - \sqrt{\beta})^2 (\lambda\mu + \bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu} + 2\sqrt{\lambda\mu\bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu}})^L \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin r \sin x r}{(1 - 2\sqrt{\beta}\cos r + \beta)^2} e^{-L\kappa r^2} dr, \quad (38)$$

where

$$\kappa = \frac{\sqrt{\lambda\mu\bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu}}}{\lambda\mu + \bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu} + 2\sqrt{\lambda\mu\bar{\lambda}\bar{\mu}}}. \quad (39)$$

Compared to Theorem 3, using this approximation we can focus only on the terms that are critical in terms of influence on predictability. For instance, the term outside the integral which is raised to L . If it is reduced, as L grows, predictability diminishes more rapidly. This implication necessitates understanding when the approximation is valid and incorporating that understanding into the problem at hand. For example, as indicated in the proof, the approximation assumes large value for K . We will evaluate this in more detail in the next section.

In the following section we focus on numerical evaluations of the predictability analysis methods in different scenarios and configurations.

3.1.4 Numerical evaluations

This section is dedicated to evaluating the proposed methods and examining the predictability in abstract systems in three subsections. First, we evaluate the spectral-based upper bound and approximations on predictability of the Geo/Geo/1/K queue. The second subsection is devoted to analyzing how dynamics of the queue affect its predictability, and in the end, multi-hop queues are analyzed when their observability is limited.

Approximation and upper bound validation

To assess the effectiveness of our proposed approximation method in Proposition 1 and the upper bound in Theorem 2, we analyze a Geo/Geo/1/K queue with default parameters $\mu = 0.5$, $\rho = 0.85$, and $K = 128$. Figure 3.4 illustrates the posterior and marginal delay distributions given various observed queue lengths for this queue.

Figure 3.4 Posterior and marginal distributions of a Geo/Geo/1/K queue with $\mu = 0.5$, $\rho = 0.85$, and $K = 128$.

In Figure 3.5, we validate the approximation method by comparing it to the exact predictability derivation presented in Theorem 1. The main finding is that the accuracy of the approximation is significantly influenced by the disparity between the observed state's forecast distribution and the marginal distribution. As illustrated in Figure 3.4, states that are closer to the marginal distribution display less accurate approximations in Figure 3.5, whereas states further from the marginal distribution (those above 16) demonstrate more accurate approximations.

Figure 3.5 Predictability evaluation for different observed states of a Geo/Geo/1/K system with $\mu = 0.5$, $\rho = 0.85$, and $K = 128$. The approximation method from Proposition 1 (dashed lines) is compared against the exact predictability derivation via Theorem 1 (solid lines).

Figure 3.6, shows the same setup as Figure 3.5, but with the full spectral-based upper bound in Theorem 2 (UB1). It is evident from the figure that unlike the approximation method, the upper bound is tighter for lower queue sizes. As the queue size grows, the distance between the exact curve and the bound increases. Due to poor performance, the spectral gap based upper bound (UB2) is not involved in this analysis.

Figure 3.6 Predictability evaluation for different observed states of a Geo/Geo/1/K system with $\mu = 0.5$, $\rho = 0.85$, and $K = 128$. The full spectral-based upper bound from Theorem 2 (dashed lines) is compared against the exact predictability derivation via Theorem 3 (solid lines).

In the next analysis, we apply state aggregation on the same queue. Figure 3.7 illustrates four levels of sequential and even state aggregations: no aggregation, 2-state aggregation, 4-state aggregation, and 8-state aggregation. The results show higher levels of aggregation lead to a less predictable system and a more rapid decline of predictability. The evaluation is illustrated as dashed lines in Figure 3.7 where the approximation closely follows the numerical derivation. However, it is important to note that the current approach involves an even aggregation of states. Future research could investigate uneven state aggregation to identify potential optimization strategies that might better balance the trade-off between observations' overhead and predictability.

Figure 3.7 Predictability of a Geo/Geo/1/K queue, under different under different state aggregation levels and $\rho = 0.85, \mu = 0.5$. Solid lines illustrate numerical derivation and dashed lines the approximation using proposition 1.

Geo/Geo/1/K dynamics and predictability

To investigate the predictability in systems with Geo/Geo/1/K queues further, next, we examine the impact of the observed state and utilization factor (ρ). In the following analysis, we obtain predictability using Theorem 3 and Proposition 1. Figure 3.8 demonstrates the predictability when $\mu = 0.4$, $K = 100$, and the observed state x is either 3, 9, or 15 times greater than the expected state denoted by χ . It is evident from the figure that the sojourn time is more predictable when there is a significant backlog or when the queue length is substantially different from the expected queue length. This implies that the queue remains predictable for a certain duration into the future, and we have sufficient information to predict the delay distribution for a period of time before it converges to the stationary delay distribution. In real systems, especially those operating in high utilization regimes where efficiency is critical, this analysis highlights the importance of monitoring the queue. High utilization often corresponds to more significant backlog situations, where predictability is maintained for longer durations.

Figure 3.8 Predictability of a single Geo/Geo/1 queue, under different configurations. Solid lines illustrate numerical derivation and dashed lines the approximation in Proposition 1.

In Definition 2, we introduced the time frame during which the delay predictions remain distinct from the stationary distribution, referred to as epsilon-predictable horizon. Figure 3.9 illustrates the epsilon-predictable horizon of different Geo/Geo/1 queues. For queues with higher utilization, as predictability degrades more slowly, the forecasting system can sample the queue length less frequently and reduce the monitoring overhead. In a queue with a higher arrival rate, but similar service rate, the stationary state distribution is wider, and its expected queue length is larger, while the conditional distribution is unchanged. Therefore, the Total Variation difference between the forecast and marginal distributions decreases slower as we increase the lead time, resulting in a slower decline in predictability, as illustrated in the figures.

Figure 3.9 Epsilon-predictable horizon of Geo/Geo/1/K queuing system, under different configurations and $\epsilon = 0.1$

Figure 3.9 illustrates epsilon-predictable horizon for Geo/Geo/1/K queues with $K = 50$, highlighting its relationship with both the utilization factor and the service rate. In this figure, we observe that epsilon-predictable horizon increases in higher utilizations and lower service rates. Epsilon-predictable horizon is related to the state that results in minimum distance between the forecast and marginal distributions, which is close to the expected queue length.

Predictability of multi-hop Geo/Geo/1 queues

In this part, we evaluate two multi-hop scenarios under different levels of observability. In the first case, illustrated in Figure 3.10, we evaluate predictability for a system that consists of 5 tandem Geo/Geo/1/K queues, all with the same service rate $\mu = 0.4$ and highly congested with the observed state of 15χ . We consider 3 different configurations: observations that include all 5 queues, observations including only the first 3 queues, and observations including only the first queue. We used Equations 33 and 34 to derive exact predictability curves shown via solid lines. As was expected, predictability decreases as our ability to observe the system declines. Then the dashed line curves show the upper bounds derived using Lemma 5 and Theorem 3 (UB). In the first case where all queues are observable, we derived the bound by summing up the predictability of all hops. However, when it comes to the case with only one observable queue, the bound equals the predictability of that queue. This is because if a component is not observable, its predictability is zero and will not contribute to the sum in Equation 35. Therefore, we have $D_n(L) \leq D_n^{(1)}(L)$, which constitutes the upper bound for the partially observable system.

Figure 3.10 Predictability of a 5-hop tandem Geo/Geo/1 queuing system under different observability levels. All queues have the same service rate of $\mu = 0.4$ and $\lambda = 0.32$.

The next scenario we analyze in multi-hop networks involves a queue that becomes a bottleneck and how its observability affects predictability. Since this queue will contribute more to the end-to-end delay, if it is not observable, we expect the predictability to decrease significantly. In a setup, we examine three tandem Geo/Geo/1/K queues with an arrival rate of $\lambda = 0.34$, where the middle queue has a lower service rate, i.e., the service rates are $\mu^{(1)} = 0.4, \mu^{(2)} = 0.38$, and $\mu^{(3)} = 0.4$ respectively. Suppose $\chi^{(m)}$ as the expected queue length of hop m . All three queues are again highly congested with the observed states of 10 times their expected queue size. As shown in Figure 3.11, we consider four different configurations: the observations include all three queues, the observations include only the first queue, the observations include only the last queue, and the observation include only the bottleneck queue. Note that in tandem M/M/1 queues, when the system is in equilibrium, regardless of the service rates, all queues will have the same arrival rate as the first queue [Tho12]. Using Equations 33 and 34, we derive exact predictability curves shown via solid lines. The figure indicates that the observation of one of the less utilized queues provides similar benefits in terms of predictability. However, observing these queues alone results in significantly lower predictability compared to the scenario in which only the bottleneck queue is observable. The predictability of the latter case is very close to that of complete observability.

Similar to Figure 3.10, the dashed lines represent the upper bound derived using Lemma 5 and Theorem 3 (UB) and it is less tight when the predictability of all hops is summed up. Note that $\chi^{(1)} = \chi^{(3)}$ due to similar arrival and service rates.

Figure 3.11 Predictability of a 3-hop tandem Geo/Geo/1/K queuing system with a bottleneck queue in the middle. Service rates are 0.4, 0.38, and 0.4 respectively. Arrival rate: 0.34.

3.1.5 Key takeaways

- A formal definition of predictability in systems research is introduced, which comprises understanding a system to be predictable (or more predictable) if out of current system state a different stochastic behavior can be deduced than what would be deduced from steady state conditions. Systems where current conditions do not allow any more refined stochastic characterization than what can be deduced for steady state are termed unpredictable.
- We show that under this definition bounds on the predictability can be derived for a wide class of Markovian systems. The analysis is validated numerically.
- In the numerical analysis we further study the consequences of the definitions and the bounds with respect to Markovian queuing systems. We show that predictability decreases with longer prediction time horizons, while generally speaking more extreme instantaneous system states (like long backlog) lead to a higher predictability. Imprecise system knowledge (for

instance due to unknown partial backlogs in multi-hop systems) leads interestingly only in some cases to a degradation of predictability, while outdated system state knowledge is equivalent (in terms of predictability implications) with considering longer time horizons.

3.2 Probabilistic latency prediction for wireless networks

Recent enhancements like Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC) in 5G have strived to narrow the gap between application demands and actual wireless performance. However, meeting precise latency bounds in a probabilistic sense remains an open problem, as even small deviations from target deadlines can severely impact time-critical tasks.

Figure 3.12 Illustration of TSN cycles over a wireless link, showing a broad reception time profile caused by the stochastic nature of wireless delays, which may change over time. Orange times spans refer to idle medium durations, i.e. not scheduled by TSN.

Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) standards under IEEE 802.1 have introduced a set of traffic-shaping mechanisms to achieve bounded latency in switched Ethernet networks.

Wired networks employing TSN mechanisms operate under the assumption that packet end-to-end delays are both minimal and tightly bounded, exhibiting a narrow distribution that remains largely constant over time. In contrast, wireless links present a fundamentally different challenge. As illustrated in Figure 3.12, the reception time of a packet over a wireless link not only spans a much wider distribution but also fluctuates as the link conditions evolve. Factors such as interference, channel fading, and the variable nature of retransmission protocols like HARQ contribute to this dynamic behavior. Consequently, while TSN can rely on stable delay characteristics in wired environments, wireless networks demand advanced modeling techniques capable of capturing the temporal evolution and inherent variability of the delay distribution.

Given these challenges, it is insufficient to rely solely on current delay statistics; instead, it is crucial to forecast the evolution of latency over time. Temporal probabilistic prediction models aim to estimate the complete delay distribution over multiple future time steps, capturing both short- and long-term dependencies.

In previous works, specifically traditional model-based approaches, such as network calculus and queuing theory, researchers rely on strong and often unrealistic assumptions that fail to capture the intricate dynamics of modern systems. Recently data-driven methods have emerged as a promising alternative. Recent advancements in deep learning have further demonstrated the superior performance of data-driven approaches for delay characterization. By leveraging measurement data collected from real systems, these methods utilize machine learning techniques to uncover and learn

relationships between the delay and other influencing factors. We next investigate such approaches further.

3.2.1 Prediction Approach

During a sequence of packet transmissions, upon the arrival of packet n , our objective is to predict not only its delay distribution but also the delay distributions of the subsequent packets $n + 1, \dots, n + L - 1$. Accurate prediction requires integrating comprehensive condition information from all relevant processes affecting packet transmission. Temporal dependencies imply that relying solely on the most recent state may be insufficient; historical data can reveal trends indicating improving, deteriorating, or stabilizing conditions. Hence, we consider the previously observed H packet delay pairs up to the arrival of packet n to estimate the conditional probability:

$$\mathbb{P}[Y_{n+l} \mid \mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{x}_{n-1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{n-H+1}]$$

for $l = 0, 1, \dots, L-1$, where Y_{n+l} denotes the delay of packet $n + l$, and \mathbf{x} denotes the conditions vector.

The method that we propose in the following aims to predict the end-to-end packet delay distributions by leveraging historical delay data and contextual dependencies. Given the impracticality of closed-form solutions, we adopt a data-driven approach, using past packet delays to forecast future delays (up to L packets ahead). The approach consists of three main steps:

1. **Tokenization:** Encoding historical observations into fixed-dimensional representations (tokens).
2. **Deep Learning Architecture:** Utilizing temporal or non-temporal models such as Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLP)s, Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTM)s or Transformers to capture general or time-dependent relationships.
3. **Parametric Distribution Prediction:** Generating parameters for a probabilistic delay distribution such as a Gaussian mixture model (GMM).

To incorporate historical data into a deep-learning model, we begin by mapping each packet delay context \mathbf{x}_n into a fixed-dimensional representation of size S , which we treat as a *token*. Formally, we define an embedding function to convert \mathbf{x}_n to \mathbf{u}_n , and \mathbf{u}_n encapsulates the relevant statistics of the packet (e.g., size and periodicity) and contextual features (e.g., Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) index, scheduling phase, number of retransmissions, queue length). The tokenizer function concatenates the individual embeddings of these features and processes them through a MLP (FeatureCombiner), which maps the resulting vector onto an S -dimensional space:

$$[\text{Emb}_1, \text{Emb}_2, \dots] \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^S.$$

In other words, we can view the tokenizer as a learnable feature extractor that transforms raw input data \mathbf{X}_n into a more compact, delay-predictive representation \mathbf{u}_n . By training it jointly with the rest of the model, relevant features can be extracted automatically, eliminating the need for extensive manual feature engineering. Moreover, disaggregating the embedding function from the main temporal model allows for more flexible transfer across different tasks or datasets. We then collect the most recent H tokenized observations. By stacking these token vectors, we obtain a two-dimensional matrix $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times S}$, which serves as the input to our temporal deep learning model. This sequence \mathbf{U} captures the immediate past network states and delays, providing sufficient temporal context to infer evolving congestion levels, channel conditions, and scheduling dynamics.

Once the embedding matrix $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times S}$ is formed by stacking H tokenized observations, the next step is to capture temporal dependencies and generate predictions for future packet delays. In what follows, we describe two commonly used deep-learning frameworks for this task: (i) a recurrent architecture (e.g., LSTM) and (ii) an attention-based architecture (e.g., Transformer). Our goal in this part of the approach is to produce a tensor $\Theta \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times V}$, where L is the number of future packets for which we want to predict the delay distribution, and V is the dimensionality of the parametric density function's parameters (e.g., mean, variance, and weights for a Gaussian mixture model (GMM)) which fully characterizes the predicted distribution for the delay of packet $n + l$ for $l \in \{0 : L - 1\}$.

Next, we describe the two proposed approaches for converting a sequence of delay tokens into a sequence of distribution parameters: one that uses a recurrent architecture (e.g., LSTM) and another that employs an attention-based architecture (e.g., Transformer). While both LSTMs and Transformers have proven effective in capturing temporal dependencies, they possess distinct characteristics. On the one hand, LSTMs, renowned for their ability to handle sequential data, excel at modeling long term dependencies through their memory cells. However, they can be computationally expensive, especially for long sequences. Transformers, on the other hand, leverage self-attention mechanisms to weigh the importance of different input tokens, enabling them to capture complex relationships between distant elements. While Transformers often outperform LSTMs in tasks requiring long-range dependencies, they can be less efficient for shorter sequences. Given the varying nature of packet delay patterns, which can exhibit both short-term fluctuations and long-term trends, we believe that a comparative analysis of both architectures is essential to identify the most suitable approach for our problem [HS97], [VSP+17]. A recurrent neural network processes the input tokens *sequentially* using a recurrent cell, to compile the historical information into a final hidden embedding.

In Transformers, in contrast to recurrent-based models, rely on self-attention mechanisms to capture dependencies across the entire input sequence. The key building block is the *multi-head self-attention* module, which weighs the relevance of each input token against every other token to compute a contextual representation. The encoder-decoder Transformer effectively captures historical trends and future dependencies by decoupling past encoding from future decoding, enforcing causality, and enabling parallel computations. This design is especially suited for multi-step predictions of packet delay distributions, offering scalability.

Next, we examine the final probabilistic representation layer, which uses the raw parameters Θ to compute the delay probabilities. Rather than predicting a single point estimate of future delay, we aim to model the *entire* delay distribution. Such distributional forecasts are vital for time-sensitive applications that require robust estimates of worst-case or high-percentile latencies. This task falls under the umbrella of Conditional Density Estimation (CDE), where we learn a mapping from input conditions (historical and contextual data) to the parameters of a chosen parametric distribution.

We use Mixture Density Network (MDN) with GMM that can be used to capture potentially multimodal delay behaviors, characterized by a set of weights, means, and variances as shown via a GMM with two centers in Figure 3.13. Mathematically, we denote the parametric distribution for packet $n + l$ as $P(y_{n+l} | \theta_{n+l})$, where θ_{n+l} are parameters output by the neural network. Once these parameters are obtained, we can derive quantities of interest (e.g., mean, variance, or percentile thresholds such as the 95th percentile) to facilitate admission control, resource allocation, and other TSN-driven optimization tasks.

Figure 3.13 Gaussian mixture model example with 2 components and their parameters denoted by μ as mean, σ as variance, and w as mixture weight.

To train the proposed models, we first build a dataset of historical sequences and corresponding future delays. Each training sample contains:

- *Historical window*: A sequence of H past delay context vectors
- *Future window*: The subsequent L delay values

Having a dataset of certain number of sequences, we define the loss value as the Negative Log-Likelihood (NLL) across all future steps of all sequences in the training dataset or batch. Then, the optimizer can minimize that by adjusting the weights and biases in the neural network. By minimizing NLL, the model is encouraged to match the full distribution of the delay, rather than just a single statistic.

By simultaneously fitting the parameters of a parametric distribution and leveraging temporal context, the model learns both short- and long-range dependencies in packet delay. As conditions evolve in online scenarios, newly observed samples can be integrated to continually refine model estimates, ensuring robust and adaptive latency prediction in 5G/6G-TSN networks.

During online deployment, the model continually updates its input sequence with newly observed packet delays and network conditions, refining its understanding of the system as it evolves. This adaptive nature is particularly relevant in 5G/6G networks, where user mobility and varying traffic loads can alter channel conditions and resource availability over time.

3.2.2 Evaluations

In this section, we detail the experimental setup used to assess our proposed approaches and explain the evaluation methodology. This includes the implementation of the proposed approaches, the key performance metrics for delay prediction, the model variants, and their implementation. Additionally, we describe the different configurations and comparison schemes used in our experiments.

A. Data Collection and training Setup

All proposed machine learning models (LSTM, Transformer, MLP-based hybrids, etc.) were implemented in PyTorch. We used a uniform training and inference pipeline, ensuring that any variations in model performance arise from architectural differences rather than implementation details. Training and evaluations were conducted on two Dell R450 servers, each equipped with an NVIDIA L4 GPU featuring 24 GB memory, an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4314 CPU operating at 2.40 GHz, and 128 GB RAM.

Figure 3.14 Data collection setup with EDAF and OpenAirInterface5G on uplink direction.

To collect real-world data, we employed a Software-Defined Radio (SDR)-based 5G system using *OpenAirInterface5G* on the ExPECA testbed [KSG+20], [MMR+24] via the setup shown in Figure 3.14. ExPECA is designed as an edge-computing test environment, comprising servers and SDRs connected through a flexible networking fabric, all synchronized in time using the Precision Time Protocol (PTP). These components are deployed in an underground facility with no external interference, making it well-suited for reproducible, end-to-end, time-sensitive wireless experiments. We elaborate about the capabilities and implementation details of ExPECA in our previous work in [MMR+24]. We also leveraged the previously published work “End-to-End Delay Analytics Framework” (EDAF) to gather and preprocess the end-to-end delay measurements and associated context (e.g., packet size, MCS index, number of retransmissions) [MTS+24]. The *EDAF* framework can extract comprehensive timely information about the 5G processes that manage packet transmission, thus facilitating an in-depth analysis of network performance with respect to end-to-end (E2E) delay. Its core objective is to capture timestamps and key metadata from the packet’s journey in realtime, starting at the application node (UE side) and ending at the server node (gNB side).

Deployment Setup: We ran experiments on two nodes within the ExPECA testbed: SDR-04 (gNB) and SDR-07 (UE). This link has line of sight connection with 20m distance and the MCS index of this connection was around 20 with RSRP of -90dbm.

Traffic Patterns: Periodic packet arrivals, with interarrival times ranged from 10ms to 100ms, with packet sizes varying from 100B to 1000B.

Data Volume: Over the course of the experiments, we collected more than one million packet samples along the same link, yielding a large and diverse dataset of delay measurements under different load conditions and channel states.

The final dataset was preprocessed (e.g., outlier filtering, synchronization, normalization of features) and stored for offline training and evaluation. We partitioned the data into training (80%), validation (20%), and test sets (separate larger set) to facilitate hyperparameter tuning and unbiased performance assessments.

To evaluate each model’s ability to forecast future latency distributions under realistic 5G conditions, we use the following core KPIs:

- **Negative Log-Likelihood (NLL):** This standardized measure for probabilistic modeling also serves as our training loss. Lower NLL values indicate that the predicted distributions more closely align with the observed delay data.
- **Coverage Probability (e.g., 99% Coverage):** Captures how frequently the actual delay falls within the model’s high-confidence region (e.g., the 99th percentile) of its predicted distribution.
- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE) & Variance:** While the focus is on distribution-based prediction, MAE and variance still provide insight into average prediction error and its spread compared to ground truth.

Beyond accuracy, we also track the following efficiency metrics, which play a decisive role in determining practical usability:

- **Data Efficiency:** Assesses how much training data is needed for the model to reach a certain performance level. In rapidly changing 5G/6G-TSN environments, reducing data collection overhead can be crucial, as it influences how often retraining is required.
- **Training Time:** Complex neural architectures with large datasets can incur substantial computational overhead. We therefore measure training time under consistent hardware and batch-size conditions to gauge each model’s scalability.
- **Model Size:** We record the total number of parameters and observe how both performance and training time grow with the historical window size H and prediction horizon L . Approaches that demand significantly higher capacity or exhibit drastic slowdowns for large H or L are less practical in real-world deployments.

Unless otherwise specified, all metrics are evaluated on a dedicated test set to ensure an unbiased measure of generalization performance.

All models terminate with an MDN head that estimates a Gaussian mixture distribution (8 components, 24 parameters). An affine transform is applied to the delay dimension, and small Gaussian noise (e.g., standard deviation of 0.1) is injected during training to enhance robustness.

In Table 3.1, we summarize the core models and how they handle both *context extraction* and *future delay generation*:

Table 3.1 Summary of models used in comparison

Model Name	Context Extraction	Generation
MLP	Non-temporal feed-forward	-
LSTM	LSTM	LSTM
TRANSFORMER	Encoder	Decoder

We benchmark multiple architectural variants, feature sets, and data regimes to evaluate the robustness and scalability of the state-of-the-art models and our solution in the following two subsections. Note that we vary the historical and future window lengths together as $(H : L)$ changes among (10 : 10), (20 : 20), (50 : 50), and (100 : 100). These settings mimic diverse latency constraints and prediction horizons.

B. Prediction Accuracy

Figure 3.15 and Figure 3.16 summarize the prediction performance of MLP, LSTM, and Transformer for varying future window lengths L . Figure 3.15 shows the standardized test NLL, reflecting both how well each model’s predicted distribution aligns with the observed delays and how effectively it captures predictive uncertainty. Across all horizons, the Transformer achieves the lowest (best) NLL, demonstrating that its attention mechanism excels at modeling the temporal dependencies and variability of the delay process. The LSTM ranks second, leveraging its gating structure to track sequential patterns more reliably than the simpler MLP, which sees its NLL grow considerably for large L .

Figure 3.16 depicts the MAE, a point estimate of prediction error. Here too, the Transformer consistently outperforms both the LSTM and MLP, with the LSTM maintaining an intermediate level of accuracy. As L increases, the feedforward MLP struggles the most, indicating that models with recurrent or attention-based mechanisms capture long-range dependencies more effectively.

In Figure 3.17, we further analyze the standardized NLL for streams with different packet interarrival times. Both the LSTM and Transformer find it more challenging to predict delays when packets arrive rapidly (short interarrivals), underscoring the increased temporal coupling in faster traffic. However, the Transformer still delivers lower NLL than the LSTM, with a wider gap in challenging scenarios. This highlights that attention-based architectures provide a robust framework for learning complex dependencies, even in high intensity scenarios.

Figure 3.15 Standardized test negative loglikelihood (NLL) of packet delay for different models against various prediction horizons.

Figure 3.16 Mean absolute error (MAE) of packet delay for different models against various prediction horizons.

Figure 3.17 Standardized test negative loglikelihood (NLL) of packet delay for different models Decomposed for various packet inter-arrival times.

(a) Prediction horizon $L=5$

(b) Prediction horizon $L=20$

(c) Prediction horizon $L=50$

Figure 3.18 Empirical coverage derived using different predictors against ground truth.

Figure 3.18 evaluates the empirical coverage of prediction intervals for MLP, LSTM, and Transformer models at prediction horizons $L = 5, 20, \text{ and } 50$. The dashed diagonal line represents perfect calibration, where the empirical coverage matches the nominal target coverage $(1-\alpha)$. Deviations below the line indicate over-coverage (predicted distributions are too wide), while deviations above the line indicate under-coverage (predicted distributions are too narrow).

Our results indicate several critical observations. For $L = 5$, the MLP aligns closest to the perfect calibration line, particularly for higher confidence levels (e.g., 99%). This indicates that for short prediction horizons, the MLP provides well-calibrated intervals. By contrast, the LSTM and Transformer over-cover across all target confidence levels, generating wider prediction intervals. While over-coverage is less risky than under-coverage, it may lead to inefficiencies in certain applications. As the horizon grows, for $L = 20$, the MLP starts to show under-coverage, especially at higher confidence levels. This suggests that the MLP fails to properly account for increasing uncertainty in longer-term predictions. The LSTM and Transformer continue to exhibit over-coverage but remain consistent in their behavior, maintaining wider intervals that prioritize robustness. At the longest horizon ($L = 50$), the MLP significantly under-covers, particularly at extreme confidence levels (e.g., 99%). This growing undercoverage reflects the MLP's limitations in capturing temporal dependencies. Meanwhile, the LSTM and Transformer maintain their over-coverage behavior, showing that they reliably account for the increasing uncertainty at extended horizons, albeit conservatively.

These findings are particularly important as they highlight that achieving low NLL or MAE values does not necessarily guarantee well-calibrated prediction intervals. In practical applications, such as delay prediction in 5G/6G-TSN networks, the choice of model depends on the trade-off between calibration, robustness, and efficiency. While the MLP performs well for short-term predictions, its inability to adequately model uncertainty over long horizons limits its applicability. The LSTM and Transformer, with their consistent over-coverage, provide more reliable predictions in risk-sensitive settings, where underestimating uncertainty can lead to adverse outcomes.

C. Learning Efficiency

To assess learning efficiency, we train and evaluate each model on subsets of the dataset containing 1k, 5k, 10k, and 20k samples, and examine how performance improves as training size increases. Figure 3.19 shows the standardized test NLL of packet delay as a function of the training dataset size. Both the transformer and LSTM exhibit superior performance compared to the MLP. MLP struggles with small training sizes due to its inability to capture sequential dependencies, resulting in significantly higher NLL. As training size increases, the gap between the MLP and the other models grows, indicating that with more data, the MLP cannot compensate for its architectural limitations.

Figure 3.20 illustrates the training time per sample as a function of the prediction horizon length (L). The MLP consistently exhibits the lowest training time due to its simple feedforward architecture and lack of sequential dependencies. The LSTM, by contrast, demonstrates significantly longer training times, particularly for larger horizons. This is because LSTMs process sequences sequentially, with a computational complexity of $O(L \cdot d^2)$, where L is the sequence length and d is the embedding size. In contrast, the Transformer, while theoretically more expensive ($O(L^2 \cdot d)$), benefits from parallel processing, enabling it to handle entire sequences simultaneously. Moreover, optimized implementations in deep learning libraries allow the Transformer to leverage modern hardware efficiently, resulting in faster training times than the LSTM for most horizons, despite its higher

theoretical cost. As the horizon length increases, the Transformer’s ability to scale effectively with sequence length becomes apparent, making it a practical choice for long-horizon predictions.

Figure 3.21 examines the impact of token size (embedding dimension) on the Transformer’s performance and parameter efficiency. The results reveal a clear trade-off: increasing the token size reduces the standardized NLL, improving the model’s ability to capture complex patterns and dependencies. However, this improvement comes at the cost of a quadratic increase in the number of model parameters, leading to larger memory requirements and potential overfitting risks. For example, moving from a token size of 8 to 24 reduces the NLL significantly, but also increases the number of parameters from approximately 25k to 200k. This trade-off highlights the importance of selecting an appropriate token size that balances performance and computational efficiency. For the dataset used in this study, a token size of 16 achieves a favorable balance between performance and model complexity.

These results demonstrate the strengths and weaknesses of each model with respect to learning efficiency:

- The Transformer offers superior performance in terms of data efficiency, quickly reducing NLL with fewer samples, and achieves faster training times than the LSTM, especially for long horizons, thanks to its parallelizable architecture.
- The LSTM, while slower and less efficient in data-limited regimes, still provides competitive performance due to its strong temporal modeling capabilities.
- The MLP is computationally efficient in terms of training time but lacks the ability to reach comparable performance levels, making it less suitable for sequential tasks with limited data availability.

In summary, the Transformer stands out as the most efficient model in terms of both data and training time, particularly for long-horizon predictions, but careful consideration of token size is necessary to balance accuracy and model complexity.

Figure 3.19 Standardized test NLL of packet delay for different models against the size of the training dataset.

Figure 3.20 Training time per sample for different models against the prediction horizon length. The number of training samples is 5k.

Figure 3.21 Standardized test NLL of packet delay for the transformer model trained with different token sizes. The number of parameters for the models also are shown. Number of training samples are 50k and the prediction horizon is set to L = 50.

Transformers train faster than LSTMs in practice because they leverage parallel processing, while LSTMs process sequences sequentially, making them harder to accelerate on GPUs. Unlike LSTMs, which must compute each time step one after another with a complexity of $O(L \cdot d^2)$, Transformers handle entire sequences simultaneously, making efficient use of modern hardware optimized for large matrix multiplications, despite their theoretical complexity of $O(L^2 \cdot d)$.

Additionally, deep learning libraries implement highly optimized kernels for Transformer computations, further improving speed. While Transformers have a higher theoretical computational cost, their ability to fully utilize GPUs and handle large batches efficiently often results in significantly lower training times compared to LSTMs, especially for long sequences.

We presented a probabilistic delay prediction framework that leverages deep temporal models to capture the complex dynamics of 5G/6G-TSN networks. Our experiments reveal that attention-based models, particularly Transformers, are more adept at capturing long-term dependencies compared to simple feed-forward architectures, leading to lower negative log-likelihood values over extended prediction horizons. The LSTM model demonstrated intermediate performance and proved effective in scenarios with strong temporal coupling, albeit at the cost of longer training times.

Our multi-step prediction approach, which forecasts complete delay distributions rather than single point estimates, provides a more detailed view of future network behavior—a feature that is largely

absent in existing literature. The evaluation on a real-world SDR-based 5G testbed also highlighted practical trade-offs: while the Transformer benefits from parallel processing, its performance is influenced by token size and dataset volume. Overall, our findings suggest that advanced deep learning techniques can capture delay uncertainty in wireless networks, but careful tuning and model selection are essential for balancing predictive accuracy and computational efficiency in practical deployments.

3.2.3 Key takeaways

Unlike traditional TSN, where packet delays are predictable and tightly bounded, 5G/6G introduces stochastic variations due to channel fading, interference, and retransmissions. In this section we presented a deep-learning-based framework capable of incorporating MLPs, LSTMs and Transformers to predict the full probability distribution of end-to-end delays rather than just point estimates. By leveraging historical network states and encoding them into tokenized representations, the proposed approach provides multi-step probabilistic delay predictions, enabling adaptive scheduling and resource allocation. The evaluation on an SDR-based 5G testbed demonstrates that the Transformer model significantly outperforms traditional methods in capturing both short- and long-term dependencies in delay variations. This methodology is particularly valuable for 5G/6G-TSN integration, where ensuring deterministic latency over inherently variable wireless links is critical for applications like industrial automation, real-time control, and autonomous systems.

4 Architectural aspects of performance monitoring and prediction

In this section we analyze learning architectures and model overhead analysis, as well as architectural aspects of observability for the measurements and the online monitoring during network operation.

4.1 Overhead modeling for learning architectures

Recently, many Machine Learning (ML)-based services have been supported over wireless networks. Moreover, 5G/6G networks can utilize the ML model to optimize resource allocation and forecast network traffic [PPK+23] [JMA+23]. Traditionally, training ML models is a huge bottleneck due to requiring vast amounts of data at a centralized location, which involves collecting data from numerous edge devices connected over a network (a.k.a. Centralized Learning (CL)). Therefore, the centralized approach can pose significant challenges if communication resources are costly, which can be the case in e.g., 5G/6G networks when data for CL is collected from wireless devices. In contrast to CL, the distributed approach (e.g., Federated Learning (FL)) can train ML models without sharing raw data among edge devices and a centralized location. However, the distributed approach still requires repeated exchange of ML models over the network.

Both CL and FL require different amounts of communication and compute resources due to their difference in the way learning of ML models is accomplished [DPK+23]. Furthermore, the total training time in both schemes is highly dependent on various communication and learning parameters. For example, the total training time in CL is impacted by the amount of training data, while the size of the model will impact the training time in FL. Consequently, we consider two ML algorithms of different complexity in our analysis, for which we use two real algorithms as references. Typically, image classification may use a large data set and require a large model size (represented as High-load learning (HI)). As a Low-load learning scenario (LO), ML-based 5G/6G network statistics analysis (e.g., for network QoS prediction [MSG23], [DET23-D21], [DET24-D42]) can be selected (i.e., using a small

ML model and a dataset having a small size). These two different learning cases as examples of ML models with different complexity would significantly impact the training time of CL and FL.

The previous works studied 1) comparison of CL and FL in wireless environments [DPK+23] [AMI21] and 2) FL training optimization in wireless environments [TBZ+19] [WTS+19] [HLC+23]. Asad et al. [AMI21] compared CL and FL in wireless systems. This work analyzed the accuracy of the ML model according to the training parameter (e.g., the number of clients). Drainakis et al. [DPK+23] analyzed the trade-off in energy consumption and accuracy of CL and FL in LTE and WiFi environments. Tran et al. [TBZ+19] proposed an optimization scheme for FL in wireless network environments, and the optimization problem considered energy consumption, accuracy of the learning model, and total training time. Wang et al. [WTS+19] proposed the local epoch optimization method for FL, which guarantees ML model accuracy by saving wireless resources in constrained wireless environments. Han et al. [HLC+23] proposed a joint optimization algorithm of client scheduling, training time, and energy consumption for a ML-based classification application using FL.

Figure 4.1 Learning procedures for the two learning schemes.

In contrast to the abovementioned works, our work systematically investigates all relevant parameters impacting learning over a 5G/6G network for the two learning schemes and for different ML application scenarios (i.e., HI and LO). It is difficult to measure how much training overhead is changed by each parameter since training overheads of CL and FL are hugely varying depending on both wireless network and learning parameters. To quantitatively investigate the impact of parameters on the training overhead, we conduct the factorial design, which is one of the solutions for sensitivity analysis. From the factorial design, the effects of parameters are evaluated by the total training time. Then, the highly affecting parameters (i.e., main parameters) are selected for the comparison of CL and FL.

4.1.1 System model

In this section, we introduce the system model used for analyzing the performance of the two learning schemes over 5G/6G networks.

Learning schemes

Figure 4.1 shows the learning procedure of CL and FL. For both schemes, one server (e.g., located at the base station or edge cloud) and J User Equipment devices (UEs) (running client applications) participate in the training. We assume that prior to the initiation of training, all UEs have a local dataset that is used for the training of the ML model. The amount of data transmitted by a UE is denoted by D (in bytes). We consider the following operations for CL and FL:

- 1) *CL*: The learning procedure is composed of the initialization process and training process. The total training time in CL is denoted by T^{CL} . In the initialization phase, the server collects data from the clients. After that, the server trains the ML model repeatedly while reaching a certain accuracy (or the maximum number of iterations (i.e., epochs).
- 2) *FL*: In contrast to CL, FL has a different learning procedure due to its decentralized architecture and involves exchanging only the ML model among the server and clients. The size of the ML model is denoted by W . The learning procedure consists of multiple rounds. The total training time in FL is denoted by T^{FL} . Each round consists of downlink transmission of the ML model, local training in the clients, uplink transmission of the updated models, and aggregation of the updated models in the server. Typically, aggregation is conducted by averaging each parameter in model weights and time consumption for aggregation is negligible in comparison to time consumption of downlink and uplink transmissions, and local training. This round-based process is operated until reaching R rounds or achieving a specific accuracy of the ML model.

Figure 4.2 System Model for Learning Architecture.

Communications and computation model

Irrespective of the learning scheme, communication between the server and the clients is needed for exchanging data samples or ML models. We assume that the learning is provided over a 5G network as shown in Figure 4.2. The 5G network consists of two main parts: (i) 5G RAN and (ii) 5G Core network (5GC). 5G RAN comprises further J UEs and provides wireless connectivity between the UEs and 5GC. The 5G network provides a coordinator (i.e., edge server), which is the learning server in CL and the model aggregator in FL. In our model, we assume all UEs are connected to a single gNB, and that the UEs and the edge server can exchange data. We assume that all UEs have fixed positions. Each UE runs a client instance of the learning application, and the server instance of the learning application is running in an edge cloud. In the 5G network, the gNB bandwidth (BW) can be set from 5 MHz to 100 MHz [3GPP23-38306]. The maximum number of available Physical Resource Block (PRB)s in one slot N_{PRB}^{BW} is determined according to the bandwidth size and subframe numerology. C is the control

channel overhead. The ratio of uplink and downlink in the Time Division Duplex (TDD) frame, α_{TDD} , affects downlink and uplink data rate.

Based on 3GPP TS 38.306 [3GPP23-38306], the data rate (in bit per second), s , in 5G wireless environments is affected by multiple wireless parameters including the allocated PRBs, MCS index, subframe numerology, channel state (e.g., Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR)), etc. The gNB is assumed to have multiple antenna layers (i.e., l layers of the Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) system), i.e., l antennas are installed in each UE and gNB. The number of PRBs available in the 5G system is denoted by N_{PRB}^{BW} . Note that the communication resources cannot be fully allocated for the learning procedures, which is caused by resource usage from other applications and the reserved resources for the control channel. Parameter γ is the fraction of PRBs reserved for the learning procedure. The gNB selects an MCS index corresponding to the measured SINR value and the target error rate by using link adaptation methods. We assume that the link adaptation algorithm returns a fixed MCS index that guarantees a low packet error rate based on the channel quality. The selected MCS index is converted to spectral efficiency Z . The control channel overhead C is subtracted, and uplink and downlink data are sent according to α_{TDD} , from the TDD frame configuration. We assume that the effective throughput that the network delivers to the application is approximately equal to the data rate, s . In other words, we consider the effect of packet loss and retransmissions on the overall throughput to be negligible. Therefore, the data rate can be modeled by $s = lZ \frac{N_{PRB}^{BW}}{T^\mu} (1 - C) \alpha_{TDD} \gamma$.

τ is the required number of computations to train the ML model with data. The available computational resources at the edge cloud and UEs are respectively E and ϵ . The units of τ and ϵ are the number of floating-point operations per second.

Problem statement

It is beneficial to reduce the total training time irrespective of the learning scheme taken. However, training an ML model over wireless networks is influenced by various factors that include learning and system parameters. Therefore, it is desired to analyze the effect of the parameters or configurations involved on the two different learning schemes. For instance, an increase in the size of the ML model and/or amount of data prolongs the total training time. Available wireless resources (i.e., bandwidth and PRB utilization) and channel quality (i.e., MCS index influenced by channel quality) could affect the communication time of CL and FL. Increasing the number of local epochs in FL, the total training time can be reduced. Meanwhile, from the ML application perspective, the system can decide which learning scheme would be better in one configuration but cannot decide on the wireless network parameters. In this work, we attempt to determine the degree of influence of each parameter (and their combinations) on the total training time for the two learning schemes.

4.1.2 Derivation of learning overheads

In this section, we present the formal (mathematical) learning overheads while the ML model is trained.

Training time

Both CL and FL communicate among the server and clients (i.e., the initialize process in CL and uplink and downlink process in FL). The data rate, s , is denoted as u for uplink communication and d for downlink communication.

- 1) *CL*: The training phase of CL is composed of initialization and training. During initialization, the server gathers training data from the clients. The server then trains a suitable ML model using the collected training data from the clients until the desired number of training epochs are reached. Therefore, the total time of the CL, T^{CL} can be expressed as $T^{CL} = T^{IN} + \sum_{i=1}^I T_i^{TR}$ where i and I are the epoch index and the number of epochs, respectively. T^{IN} and T_i^{TR} are the time consumption for initialization (i.e., data collection time in uplink) and training in the i -th epoch. During the initialization, the server sends the data request message to the clients (the time for the request message is very small and it can be ignored); as a response the clients start sending the training data. T^{IN} is determined by the client having the slowest data rate. Therefore, T^{IN} can be defined as $\frac{D}{\min(u)}$, where $\min(\bullet)$ is the minimum value of \bullet . In the training process, T_i^{TR} is affected by the computation power of the server in each epoch. Thus, T_i^{TR} can be modeled as $\frac{\sum J \tau}{E}$.
- 2) *FL*: The training time of FL is composed of the time needed for multiple training rounds. One round consists of downlink transmission, local training, and uplink transmission. Therefore, the training time of FL, T^{FL} , can be defined as $T^{FL} = \sum_{r=1}^R T_r^{FL}$, where T_r^{FL} is the time consumption in one round and r is denoted by the round index. In addition, R is calculated by $R = \left\lceil \frac{I}{L} \right\rceil$, where L is the number of local epochs. $\lceil \bullet \rceil$ is the ceiling function of \bullet . T_r^{FL} can be modeled as $T_r^{FL} = \max(T_r^{DL} + T_r^{LT} + T_r^{UL})$ where T_r^{DL} , T_r^{LT} , T_r^{UL} are time consumption for downlink transmission, local training, and uplink transmission of a client in round r , respectively. $\max(\bullet)$ is the maximum value of \bullet . T_r^{DL} and T_r^{UL} can be expressed as $\frac{W}{d}$ and $\frac{W}{u} T_r^{LT}$, respectively, T_r^{LT} is $L \frac{\tau}{\epsilon}$.

Communication variability

Besides training time, different resource consumption patterns can be observed according to the configuration (e.g., Low-Load (LO) and High-Load (HI) learning scenarios). Therefore, different learning schemes have different usage patterns for wireless resources. For example, CL consumes wireless resources at the beginning of the training procedure. FL consumes wireless resources periodically while exchanging the ML model among the server and clients. The deviation from the average resource usage can be formulated as communication variability, V . V is measured by using the equation $V = \frac{1}{2\bar{N}K} \sum_{k=1}^K |N_k - \bar{N}|$ where \bar{N} is the average PRB usage for the ML operation over the total training time and N_k is the number of used PRBs for the ML operation at iteration k . $|\bullet|$ is the absolute value of \bullet . Note that the communication variability is calculated until reaching a certain convergence threshold (or the maximum iterations). The communication variability is measured in Section 4.1.4. Note that we consider only the wireless link in this analysis and there are no resource limitations in wired links, like e.g. the backhaul link of the gNB.

4.1.3 Sensitivity analysis: 2^k factorial design approach

In this section, we present factorial analysis on the training time based on the models presented in Section 4.1.1.

The sensitivity analysis is conducted to find the key parameters (i.e. key factors) based on the result (or system response) so that we can easily classify which parameters could be the key factors that affect the system response (i.e., the total training time and communication variability) [MW06]. Therefore, to find the key factors, all the parameters should be investigated. From factorial design, we

can estimate how the performance is impacted by the parameters and their combinations. Let us assume there are k parameters that we could configure in the 5G/6G and learning system, and each parameter could select X options. To exhaustively investigate all the effects of the system, X^k experiments are required. The effect of the parameter (or the interaction effect of parameters) is obtained based on X^k responses by using factorial design. After getting the effects of all available combinations, we conduct regression for all the effects of combinations and then select the main factors according to the regression value.

However, it is very difficult to measure the system response from all available combinations of parameters (i.e., X^k is the system response). For example, assume there are 6 parameters and we could select 10 options for each parameter. That is, 1 million responses are required to conduct factorial design. To reduce the complexity, we conduct 2^k factorial design. Each parameter will be set with two extreme values: 1) returning a reduced response (i.e., shortening the total training time, (-)) and 2) returning an increased response (i.e., extending the total training time, (+)). Here, let Y be the linear regression model of factorial design, which can be defined as

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i X_i + \sum_{i < j} \beta_{ij} X_i X_j + \dots + \beta_{i_1 \dots i_k} X_{i_1} X_{i_2} \dots X_{i_k} + \epsilon$$

where β_0 is the average response value of the responses. β_i is the effect of parameter i , from which we can observe how much of Y changes from parameter i . β_{ij} represents the effect of interaction between parameters i and j . X_i denotes the level of response (i.e., it returns 1 if the parameter is set to (+), or otherwise it returns -1), and ϵ is the error term. The key factors will be selected according to the effects. After that, each key factor will be further investigated with multiple values.

In order to get the training time, we have measured the training times in MacBook M2 Pro.

Table 4.1 Parameter settings

Parameter	+	-
Bandwidth (BW)	10 MHz	100 MHz
PRB utilization (γ)	30 %	100 %
MCS index	5	22
Data size (D)	119 MB	7603 MB
ML model size (W)	0.226 MB	2.272 MB
The number of local epochs (LE)	1	10

Parameter choice

Wireless parameters and ML parameters are selected to analyze the total training time of CL and FL. The chosen parameters for 5G networks are bandwidth BW, PRB utilization γ , and channel quality (i.e., MCS index that affects the spectral efficiency Z). In addition, high-load (HI) and low-load (LO) cases are considered to study the impact of learning parameters on the overheads. In the high-load case, the data size D and ML model size W can be large resulting in a longer total training. In the low-load case, the data size D and ML model size W are significantly smaller compared to the high-load case. Therefore, in the factorial analysis, the learning parameters include the amount of data D , ML properties (i.e., the required number of calculations τ and ML model size W), and the number of local epochs LE . In our factorial design approach, we have 6 parameters (i.e., $k = 6$), and therefore 64 combinations of training time are evaluated in this section.

Table 4.1 shows the setting of the parameters. Based on this table, we could get the effect of each parameter and the interaction effect of parameters i . N_{PRB}^{BW} is calculated based on [3GPP22-38101]. The number of clients is set to 20. The number of MIMO layers v is set to 4, the overhead C is set to 0.14 for downlink communication and 0.08 for uplink communication based on [3GPP23-38306].

Learning task analysis

In this subsection, we analyze accuracy according to two different learning scenarios (high-load, HI, and low-load, LO, ML scenarios) since we compare training complexity in CL and FL. Figure 4.3 shows the accuracy curves of the image classification (i.e., HI) according to the number of iterations and the tail error of the latency prediction scenario (i.e., LO). Figure 4.3 (left) shows that CL converges relatively faster than FL, where it reaches 80% accuracy at the 35th epoch. FL when local epochs are set to 1, 2, 4, 5, and 10 reaches 80% accuracy after many more rounds, respectively.

Figure 4.3 (Left) Accuracy curve of image classification (HI). (Right) Normalized mean-squared error (NMSE) of latency prediction (LO).

Otherwise, FL cannot provide 80% accuracy during 800 iterations and its accuracy remains generally inferior compared to CL. From here on, the number of iterations (or the number of rounds) for HI are set according to the value when accuracy reaches 80%. Figure 4.3 (right) shows the latency prediction scenario [MSG23]. The white circles in the figure are outliers and the solid blue lines are the average values. The Normalized Mean-Squared Error (NMSE) value is measured by the tail probabilities of the predicted latency value and measured latency value. The training complexity of LO is significantly lower than that of HI (i.e., the network data dimension is significantly smaller than the image data dimension). Therefore, the number of iterations is set to 800 for both CL and FL. The ranges of NMSE values are given in which each training scheme is respectively measured from 20 trained ML models. For the measured value, the test dataset is composed of latency values when the MCS index is 5. The performance results of CL and FL show no large difference. The tail error in FL increases with the number of local epochs when the tail probability is 10⁻⁵.

Factorial analysis

Table 4.2 shows the selected factor combinations that highly affect the total training time of CL. When the combination consists of a single factor, it can be observed that four factors (i.e., data size, bandwidth, channel quality, and PRB utilization) out of seven factors influence the total training time of CL. This means the other three factors do not change the total training time. Meanwhile, data size is the factor with the highest effect compared to the other factors. The highest effect in the system (i.e., data size) is 11.40%. From combinations of two factors, the case of bandwidth and data size highly affects the total training time of CL. When the number of elements in a combination is three, the case

of bandwidth, channel quality, and data size shows 6.73% effects in the total training time of CL. This shows that for the CL the amount of training data that needs to be transferred from the devices to the central server over the wireless uplink and the capacity that is available for this transfer are the key characteristics influencing the CL training time.

Table 4.2 Highly impacted parameter combinations in CL.

Combination of parameters	Effects (%)
Data size	11.40
Bandwidth	9.90
Channel quality	8.28
PRB utilization	6.36
Bandwidth and Data size	9.59
Data size and Channel quality	8.02
Bandwidth and Channel quality	6.94
Bandwidth, Channel quality, and Data size	6.73

Table 4.3 Highly impacted parameter combinations in FL.

Combination of parameters	Effects (%)
Bandwidth	4.81
Model size	4.69
Local epoch	4.62
Channel quality	4.00
PRB utilization	3.08
Bandwidth and Model size	3.94
Local epoch and Bandwidth	3.87
Local epoch and Model size	3.78
Bandwidth and Channel quality	3.35
Channel quality and Model size	3.28
Local epoch and Channel quality	3.23
Local epoch, Bandwidth, and Model size	3.17
Local epoch, Bandwidth, and Channel quality	2.70

Table 4.3 shows the selected factor combinations that highly influence the total training time of FL. More factors affect the total training time of FL compared to CL cases and therefore, each combination of factor(s) has less percentage of the effects in the system. FL is not affected by the data size but affected by model size because FL only exchanges the ML model when the client and gNB communicate with each other. When only a single factor is considered, bandwidth shows the highest effects (i.e., 4.81%). When the number of elements in a combination is two, the case of bandwidth and model size shows the highest effect of the total training time in FL (i.e., 3.94%). From combinations of three factors, the combination of local epoch, bandwidth, and model size shows a 3.17% effect. From the results of Table 4.2 and Table 4.3, the key factors that significantly influence the training time, can be identified as wireless parameters.

4.1.4 Quantitative Analysis of key factors

In this section, we measure the identified key factors with various values. Different scenarios are analyzed, which respectively represent a small data size with a small model (LO) and a large data size with a large model (HI). Each single key factor is analyzed while keeping the key factors constant.

BW is set to 100 MHz, and PRB utilization is set to 30%. MCS index is set to 22. The numbers of local epochs and clients are set to 10 and 20, respectively.

Training time analysis

Figure 4.4 (left) shows the effect of bandwidth for the total training time in HI and LO. For HI, FL shows better performance in terms of the total training time as compared to CL. Note that the total iteration for FL is 670 times which results in a longer training time than CL (i.e., 35 times of total iteration in CL) in HI. That means that the communication overhead of CL is much higher than the communication overhead of FL. However, in LO, FL is not always better than CL because the data size is comparatively smaller than the ML model size. Only when the available bandwidth is larger than 70 MHz, CL has a lower total training time than FL.

Figure 4.4 (right) shows the effect of the number of local epochs in HI and LO. When the number of local epochs is greater than 5, both HI and LO show that FL has a lower total training time. Local epoch directly influences reduce total communication time in FL, but CL shows the same total training time. Moreover, the total training time of FL in both HI and LO decrease inverse proportional. Moreover, when the number of local epochs is greater than 5 in HI and 10 in LO, the total training time of FL is lower than CL because FL can reduce communication overhead.

Figure 4.4 Impact on the training time (CL in right figure hidden by legend).

Communication variability analysis

Figure 4.5 (a) shows the impact of available bandwidth on communication variability. In HI, FL has higher communication variability than CL. This is because CL has a very short iteration of training time, with $I = 35$. Thus, the average resource, \bar{N} is not significantly different from N . In LO, FL has always higher communication variability than CL. However, in HI, the communication variability of CL is significantly higher than that of FL. This means that the communication resources of FL keep similar resource usage over two different learning scenarios than CL.

Figure 4.5 (b) shows the impact of the number of local epochs on communication variability. In both HI and LO, the communication variability of FL increases logarithmically over the number of local epochs and that of CL is constant. In HI, when the number of local epochs is set to small values (e.g., 1–10), the communication variability of FL is not significant. On the other hand, when the number of local epochs is set to be greater than 10, the communication variability of FL increases logarithmically. In LO, the communication variability of CL is higher than the communication variability of FL when the number of local epochs is greater than 5. In FL, the total time is dominated by T^{DL} and T^{UL} when the local epoch is small and therefore \bar{N} shows no remarkable difference from N . However, the number

of downlink and uplink transmissions drastically decreases when increasing the number of local epochs, which increases communication variability.

Figure 4.5 Impact on communication variability in terms of (a) Bandwidth and (b) Local Epoch.

4.1.5 Key takeaways

- A performance model is presented that allows the quantification of 5G/6G system variables on the total training time under either federated learning or centralized learning.
- The main factors influencing total training time are bandwidth, channel quality, data and model size as well as epoch choice in case of federated learning. Interestingly, in case of centralized learning only few single parameters already have a large impact on total training time, while for federated learning the impacts are distributed over more single parameters and parameter combinations.
- More detailed performance studies reveal that no straightforward rules exist when either centralized or federated learning is advantageous. For instance, as bandwidth increases, depending on the data size, either centralized or federated learning have better training times (while for very high bandwidth federated learning always outperforms centralized learning). A key parameter is the choice of the local epoch in federated learning, which can drastically lead to longer training times.

4.2 Observability for delay performance and prediction

To assess 6G network delay performance, it is necessary to capture delay measurements that packets experience during transmission in the network. Such measurements create also data points for data-driven performance management e.g., exploiting the ML-based delay prediction as described in Section 3. In today's mobile networks such as 5G, there is no inherent capability to observe delay performance. For this reason, data-driven delay prediction as of today utilizes lab setups, where with external measurement equipment, packet delays become measurable. This may be a manageable approach to test, develop, and validate the feasibility of data-driven delay prediction methods. To make it relevant in future live mobile network operation (i.e. 5G advanced and in future 6G), delay observability needs to be integrated into the very design of the network.

4.2.1 The need and pre-requisites for observing packet delay

For service performance management, the delay perceived by the traffic flows of the applications is relevant. The delays that a 6G network introduces for those traffic flows, are all delay components from when the packet enters the 6G networks to the moment when the packet leaves the 6G network. To quantify the 6G delay, the edge-to-edge delay of the 6G network (delay between ingress (UE or UPF) and egress (UPF or UE) of the 6G system) needs to be observed, as indicated in Figure 4.6. A break-down of delay components within the 6G network has been provided in [DET23-D21]. For a connection between an application in a mobile device and an edge server, four network segments contribute to the edge-to-edge delay (see Figure 4.6). The 6G core network processes the data frames and provides connectivity to the appropriate radio access network node; the connectivity between CN nodes and the RAN nodes is provided by a transport network. In the RAN, data transmission over the radio interface is performed between the base station and the user equipment. Radio protocols are responsible for reliable and efficient data transmission over the radio interface [DET23-D21] [PAD+25] (see the lower part in Figure 4.6). In the UE device additional delay may be introduced that is not related to the radio transmission but depends rather on the device implementation architecture. Generally, the delay in the mobile network is not symmetric and can differ for uplink and downlink direction. For communication between a device and an application in an edge server, the 6G latency is introduced in both communication directions, from the device in the uplink and towards the device in downlink. For applications communicating in-between two devices, the communication from one device to the other comprises first an uplink delay from the device to the 6G core network, from where the data is further sent to the other device introducing a downlink delay.

Figure 4.6 Delay in a 5G/6G mobile network.

For a dependable network, it is required that the network can quantitatively ascertain the delivery of required service performance for the communication as it has been agreed [DET24-D13]. This requires that the network can observe the delivered delay performance, as indicated in Figure 4.7. Such observations can be used to assess the current network delay performance and track the delivered performance during the past. If a service is provided to an application by a *service level agreement* (SLA), such performance tracking allows to account for the delivered performance with regard to the SLA. Delay observations can also be used to predict future achievable delay performance. This is indicated at the bottom of Figure 4.7, where the delay observations are used to train a ML-based delay

prediction model. This allows to estimate what level of guarantee can be provided to which latency bound (see Section 3). Such information is useful for instance to decide which service request or SLAs the network can commit to, potentially trigger interactions with the application, as part of communication-compute-control co-design [GSA+25] [DET24-D13]. But predicted delay performance can also be used as part of the service assurance of the network, i.e., it is linked to the configuration and optimization of the network operation. For example, if the delay prediction indicates that delays are with non-negligible probability exceeding the agreed delay bounds, the radio resource management may be adapted to provide lower latencies. For example, the operation point of the link adaptation can be modified to target lower Block Error Rate (BLER) target levels, thereby reducing the HARQ retransmission probabilities, which dominate the tail behavior of the delay distribution. Similarly, if the delay prediction indicates that the delivered delay is significantly better (or at higher levels of guarantee) than what was agreed in the service request [DET24-D13], then the radio resource management may be adapted to allow for more delay, and thereby move to an operation point with better spectral efficiency providing higher capacity for the radio network.

Figure 4.7 Data-driven delay analysis for dependable networks.

In order to determine the delay of a packet transfer between two reference points, the time difference between the reception at the destination and transmission at the source needs to be calculated. Obviously, it is important that the time values used in determining the source and destination timing need to be related to a common reference time. Time synchronization is the general procedure to synchronize multiple elements in a distributed system to a common reference time. In the 5G and 6G networks, for measuring delay of packet transmission, the user-plane nodes of the network need to be synchronized to a common time reference. Figure 4.8 shows time synchronization for the user plane in the 5G network and the same is expected for the 6G network. 5G has standardized the support for time synchronization which allows to transfer time synchronization messages of the Precision Time Protocol (PTP) over the 5G network [GLR+20] [DET23-D22]. To do so, the 5G network first needs to synchronize its user-plane nodes (i.e. UE, gNB, UPF). Since an Orthogonal Frequency-

Division Multiplexing (OFDM)-based radio network needs to be time-synchronized, support for time synchronization is already embedded into the 5G RAN. Based on the reference time used in RAN, time synchronization is extended over the radio interface to the mobile user equipment and via the transport network to the UPF. Consequently, all user-plane nodes UE, gNB, and UPF are synchronized to a common time reference, which is the 5G clock, as shown in Figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8 Time synchronization in 5G&6G. User-plane nodes sharing a common time reference.

4.2.2 Packet delay observability through the 5G and 6G network

The time awareness enabled by time synchronized user-plane nodes allows to measure packet delays for IP packets or Ethernet frames that are transmitted through the 5G network. A straightforward approach is to timestamp a packet when it enters the 5G system at an ingress point and append this timestamp to the packet itself, so that it is carried with the packet. When the packet leaves the 5G system again at the egress point, another timestamp can be taken and the difference between the egress timestamp and the ingress time is the residence time of the packet within the 5G system, i.e., it is the packet delay of the 5G network. This timestamping mechanism has been specified for 5G in Release 16 for the purpose of time stamping PTP or gPTP (generalized PTP) messages, and it is a fundamental mechanism to enable time synchronization over 5G [GLR+20]. However, as of today this mechanism has not been specified to enable delay measurement of user-plane traffic other than PTP.

To realize time stamping of user-plane traffic, different options can be considered. Generally, timestamping for all traffic passing through the network may introduce some processing overhead. Furthermore, time stamping as described above is only feasible for the time-synchronized user plane, otherwise no common time is available to calculate the residence time. It is generally understood that time-critical applications require time-awareness, i.e., a relation to one or more reference times. Such applications are expected to use time-sensitive communication protocols end-to-end, such as Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) in Ethernet LAN networks, or Deterministic Networking (DetNet) in IP networks. Alternatively, time-critical applications can directly use the Time-Sensitive Communication (TSC) service of 5G. Support of time synchronization has been standardized in 3GPP to support time critical communication via TSN, DetNet, and TSC. For those traffic flows, it can be expected that the user-plane paths are time-synchronized. Since only those applications are considered to need time-awareness and are also sensitive to delay and packet delay variations, delay measurements could be restricted to PDU sessions or QoS flows for such traffic. Fortunately, the total data rate of time-critical

applications is typically rather low [3GPP23-22104], which leads to low overhead due to time stamping. The granularity at which packets are timestamped depends on the desired precision for the packet delay. Given that latencies in commercial 5G networks of today are in the range from few milliseconds to some 10's of milliseconds, a time precision of $\sim 100 \mu\text{s}$ seems adequate. However, the standard allows for latency optimizations that could reduce the delays by approximately one order of magnitude [LSW+19] [SWD+18], which could motivate a need for a precision around $\sim 10 \mu\text{s}$. Timestamping of user plane packets can be used for packet delay correction, as described in Section 2. As described in Section 2.2.2 (also see Figure 2.8), PDC precision of around $\sim 10 \mu\text{s}$ demonstrates a desirable precision, in order to achieve high TSN network scheduling efficiency by applying PDC in the 5G or 6G network. We conclude that a precision in the order of $10 \mu\text{s}$ may be a reasonable precision for timestamping.

Timestamps should be transmitted together with the data packet through the 5G/6G network, from ingress to egress. Different options exist, on how such a timestamp can be associated to a user plane packet. One option is to append the timestamp directly into the end user packet, which are typically either IP packets or Ethernet frames. A timestamp could be appended to the IP/Ethernet packet in an extension header of the IP packet or Ethernet frame. At the egress of the 5G/6G network, this extension header could be removed again. An alternative approach is to transport the timestamp in a protocol of the 5G or 6G network, where it is associated to the end user packet. As shown in the user plane protocol stack depicted in Figure 4.6, there is no 3GPP protocol that stretches edge-to-edge through the 5G/6G system. However, there is the General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) Tunneling Protocol for User plane data (GTP-U), which is responsible for the transport of end user packets through the core network, and the Service Data Adaptation Protocol (SDAP) and Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP), which are responsible for the end user packet transfer through the RAN. A timestamp could be carried within the GTP-U packet that transports the end user packet through the core network, and be copied over into a SDAP or PDCP packet in the RAN that transports the same end user packet.

4.2.3 Packet delay observability in the 5G or 6G RAN

When looking at packet delays in the 5G/6G network, we can separate two distinct domains, see Figure 4.9. The core network comprises one UPF that is connected to the gNB via the transport network. The large majority of time-critical applications operate in a local or regional context; as a consequence the transport network is typically of limited size. In a local deployment of a 5G/6G non-public network e.g., in a factory, the UPF and the gNB may even be located in the same server rack. Generally, the delay impact of the core and transport network is negligible compared to the delay impact of the RAN. Furthermore, there are few stochastic variations in the traffic handling in the core and transport network. In contrast, the radio access network comprises multiple elements that introduce stochastic variation into the packet delay, and the absolute delay values are significantly larger compared to the RAN, as also shown in [DET23-D21] [DET24-D42]. This motivates to separate these two delay domains and address them separately.

Figure 4.9 Distinct delay domains in the 5G/6G network: core and transport network (1) and radio access network (2).

For the core and transport network, latency monitoring can be integrated into the GTP-U protocol (see Figure 4.8), and this has already been partly specified in 3GPP for QoS monitoring. In addition, transport networks typically have their own Operations Administration and Maintenance (OAM) tools that allow for latency monitoring.

For the RAN a dedicated solution for latency observability can be introduced. It shall be noted that the UE and the gNB operate in a time-synchronized manner, as it is common in an OFDM radio interface. The UE and gNB are synchronized to a common radio frame structure, which has an own number scheme of System Frame Numbers (SFN). It shall be noted that this synchronized property of the UE and the gNB can be exploited for delay measurements, even if the user-plane time synchronization described in Sections 4.2.1– 4.2.2 and in [GLR+20] [DET23-D22] is not applied! A simple time reference in the RAN could be a counter of OFDM symbols with regard to a certain SFN frame. Typical 5G/6G spectrum ranges include mid-band, centimetric range spectrum and millimeterwave spectrum [STK+24] [PW24]. Assuming 5G-like sub-carrier spacings for these spectrum ranges of 30, 60, 120 kHz, OFDM symbol durations are approximately 35 μ s, 18 μ s, and 9 μ s, respectively. A timing precision on symbol level seems to meet well the need for packet delay observability.

As we will discuss more thoroughly, there are several benefits when delay observations can be collected in the gNB, as will be discussed in Section 4.2.4.

Uplink delay observability

In uplink, the RAN packet delay could be determined based on a RAN-specific time-stamping approach. For example, when a user plane packet is received at the UE and passed to the radio protocols where it is buffered for transmission, a timestamp can be added to the packet (e.g., in the SDAP or PDCP protocol, see Figure 4.8). The timestamp could, for example, be an OFDM symbol counter in reference to a specific “reference SFN”. When the PDCP/SDAP packet is correctly received at the gNB and is forwarded towards the core network, a similar timestamp (e.g., OFDM symbol counter) can be added, and a RAN uplink delay can be observed.

Downlink delay observability

For downlink, a similar approach can be applied as for uplink. A timestamp (e.g., an OFDM symbol counter) is taken when a packet is received from the core network and enters the radio protocols SDAP/PDCP, where it is included in a protocol header. When the packet is correctly received at the UE and delivered to higher layers, a similar timestamp is taken and a packet delay is calculated. This packet delay can be provided back to the gNB, e.g. in a measurement report.

However, for downlink also another approach can be made with lower overhead. The gNB can exploit that it knows the exact timing of events happening in the UE for downlink transmission. In this way, the gNB can determine the downlink packet delays without any specific delay report from the UE. As a baseline we assume that the 6G radio protocols are similar to the 5G radio protocols. Recent studies propose to adopt the 5G radio protocols at large for 6G [PAD+25]. Some improvements and optimizations are suggested, which include [PAD+25]: a leaner protocol design enabling processing (and latency) optimizations, harmonization of the feedback of multiple ARQ protocols, and a simplified uplink control structure that also allows to convey more reliable HARQ feedback. While not essential, in particular this last capability of very reliable HARQ feedback supports the proposed delay estimation.

The gNB receives downlink user plane packet (e.g., IP packets or Ethernet frames) and can associate a local timestamp when the packet enters the PDCP/SDAP layer. Since the gNB implements the scheduler for radio resources and transmission assignments for the downlink (DL), the gNB is also aware of how the Packet Data Unit (PDU) is segmented and transmitted via Media Access Control (MAC) transport blocks. The gNB is also aware of the timing of every MAC transport block transmission and when they have been received at the UE. After receiving the HARQ feedback information from the UE, the gNB knows which of the MAC transport blocks were correctly received and which may need a retransmission. In this way the gNB can reconstruct the UE reception status, and knows when all transport blocks have been successfully decoded and the PDCP/SDAP PDU has been reassembled that contains the user plane IP packet or Ethernet frame. The gNB can even determine, if a further delay may be introduced at the UE, e.g., to allow for re-ordering of user plane packets. When the gNB knows that an entire user-plane packet has been re-assembled at the UE and is delivered to the higher layer, it can note a local timestamp for the packet delivery. This timestamp can be compared with the timestamp that was taken when the user plane packet originally entered the gNB, and from that the packet delay is determined.

In short, the gNB-based downlink delay observability is based on the following mechanisms, as also indicated in Figure 4.10:

- The arrival of a new downlink packet is timestamped at SDAP/PDCP (marked as red in Figure 4.10),
- The transmission timing of all segments belonging to the downlink packet is tracked (marked as purple in Figure 4.10),
- The correct reception of all segments of the downlink packet (and the associated timing) is tracked based on HARQ feedback (marked as green in Figure 4.10),
- The timing for the delivery to higher layers of the received downlink packet is timestamped at the gNB.

Figure 4.10 Downlink delay observability based packet arrival and delivery timing (red), transmission timing (purple), HARQ feedback (green).

4.2.4 A delay-assuring RAN architecture

The delay observability described above can be integrated into a delay-assuring RAN architecture, as shown in Figure 4.11. This approach allows for the gNB to collect all delay related information for uplink and downlink data transmission which are directly derived from the radio protocol operation. The collected data about packet delay can be provided for analysis, e.g., to a ML-based delay predictor as described in [DET23-D21] [DET24-D42], and in Sections 3 and 4.1. The obtained insights can be used to adapt the radio resource management to assure that the delay performance for the communication service is delivered according to the service requirements. While the service assurance is focused on the RAN only, this approach can be combined with the delay observability, prediction, and assurance in the core network as described in Section 4.2.3.

Such a delay-assuring RAN architecture has several benefits:

- It can work, even if (edge-to-edge) time synchronization is not used, as it operates solely on time-awareness with regard to RAN timing;
- It facilitates a centralized learning architecture (see Section 4.1),
 - o which provides better learning performance compared to federated learning,
 - o which avoids the need for data collection transfer from the UE to the centralized learning agent, since the downlink latency can be directly observed at the gNB from the radio protocol operation. This reduces significantly the overhead for data collection for a centralized learning architecture.
 - o It allows to enhance the ML-based delay prediction towards conditional delay prediction. The packet delay collected at the gNB can be associated with the operational state of the gNB. The predictor can derive delay predictions conditioned to the state of the RAN operation.

Figure 4.11 Design proposal for a delay-aware RAN architecture.

4.2.5 Key takeaways

In order to provide a dependable communication service for time-critical applications, the 6G network needs to be able to quantitatively ascertain that it fulfils the application requirements on delay and packet delay variation. A fundamental capability for quantitative service provisioning is the capability of the network to observe the delivered delay performance.

The observed delay performance can be used for multiple purposes:

- to track and account for the delivered service performance, which may be needed to report on the fulfilment of a *service level agreement*,
- to provide a data basis for delay prediction,
- to reveal delay performance characteristics to other network domains (e.g., the TSN or DetNet domain) to facilitate multi-domain end-to-end dependable network services,
- to derive resource management strategies to ascertain the performance promises that have been made,
- in case that the performance delivered by the network is at risk of not being able to deliver on the performance goal, to interact with the application domain¹ to facilitate application adaptations towards other levels of operation or modes of operation that still allow for acceptable operation of the application.

In a mobile network, two distinct sub-domains of delay performance can be distinguished, the core and transport network, and the radio access network; those can practically be managed distinctly in their dependable service provisioning. The edge-to-edge delay performance is typically dominated by the radio access network, where novel approaches for dependable communication services are needed; for the core and transport network, established traffic engineering methods for fixed networks can provide a solid basis.

For the RAN we propose a delay-aware design, where observability of delay performance can be integrated into the 6G radio protocols, e.g., based on the inherent time synchronicity of the radio interface operation. We propose the base station to collect delay performance for uplink and downlink transmission over the RAN, and make this data available for data-driven delay prediction, enhanced with information about the operational state of the RAN.

5 RAN resource management

In this section we firstly propose solutions for application's traffic pattern alignment for the optimization of RAN scheduling. Secondly, a novel reinforcement-learning-based RAN scheduling strategy is proposed to improve availability and reliability considering environmental information. Thirdly we include a discussion on the impact of interactions and feedback between the E2E scheduler (e.g., TSN scheduler at CNC) and the 6G RAN scheduler.

5.1 Application's traffic pattern alignment for the optimization of RAN scheduling

One limitation of URLLC is the need for resource overprovisioning to achieve very low guaranteed latency values with very high reliability, which limits the overall capacity of the 5G system (5GS), as analyzed in [APJ+20]. This limitation of the network capacity motivates our focus on the primary sources of the PD and PDV in the 6GS, as discussed in [HHA+24]. As previously noted in [MTS+24], queuing delay contributes significantly to PDV. This is closely tied to the TDD configuration pattern on one hand and the arrival time of the application traffic on the other. As mentioned earlier, overprovisioning of limited wireless interface resources is necessary to achieve low PD and PDV.

¹ To this end, network exposure functions can be used that enable mechanisms of communication-compute-application co-design [DET24-D13] [GSA+25].

Consequently, reducing PDV would improve the 6GS capacity by increasing the number of users or traffic flows supported by the Radio Access Network (RAN).

In this section, and in detail in [HHA+24], we explore the potential of 3GPP-standardized features for 5G to reduce the PD and PDV by minimizing the queuing delay and propose enhancements to address the identified gaps. In the following, we define the problem for specific scenarios and outline how the queuing delay can be minimized in an ideal case. Section 5.1.2 addresses 3GPP Time-Sensitive Communication (TSC) for supporting periodic deterministic traffic and related challenges. Section 5.1.3 introduces potential TSC extensions for external networks such as TSN. Subsequently, we present measurement and simulation results for scenarios where the 3GPP-defined features could contribute to reducing PD and PDV, thereby improving the 6GS capacity.

5.1.1 Problem definition on misalignment of RAN scheduling and application traffic

For the aperiodic traffic transmission in 5G, scheduling based on dynamic grants is the most suitable approach. However, due to long handshake procedure of first requesting and then receiving a grant for each packet it becomes unsuitable and non-scalable for the periodic TSC traffic with strict requirements on low PD. On the contrary, a Configured Grant (CG) based scheduling is a more suitable option for the periodic TSC traffic. However, the main challenge with the CG-based approach lies in the link adaptation, as the Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) parameters are updated less frequently, resulting in less efficient utilization of shared channel resources compared to the grant-based approach.

Table 5.1 6G use cases with max. PD smaller than the period

6G use cases [DET23-D11]	Period (ms)	Max. PD (ms)
Exoskeleton in industrial context		
Motor/Battery status	10	1.5
Tracking user's movement		
Adaptive manufacturing		
Functional safety stop	20	10
Line movement detection	5	2.5
Smart farming		
Monitoring sensors	100	20

In this work, we focus on time-critical applications with periodic traffic generated from the applications and therefore we only consider the CG approach. Moreover, we consider the integration of the TSN with the 6GS. In this setup, it is important to highlight the presence of two independent central entities involved in scheduling. One is the CNC, responsible for the TSN network end-to-end, and the other is the RAN, which handles the scheduling of the wireless interface within the 6G TSN bridge. As a result, the traffic within the 6G TSN bridges experiences an arbitrary delay in transmitting application data due to misalignment between the reserved slot on the wireless interface and the arrival of the application traffic. To explain the problem of the alignment of the two schedulers, we show simplified data traffic from applications and the corresponding reserved resources for the radio interface of the RAN on a timeline in Figure 5.1. In this simplified example, a trade-off between the number of reserved resources and the PDV can be observed. In Figure 5.1(a), the traffic period is higher than the allowed PDV and to fulfill that, significantly more resources are required

compared to the amount of traffic to be transmitted. In other words, low PDV can be achieved at the cost of overprovisioning of the resources. Some of use cases with such traffic requirements are summarized in Table 5.1.

Figure 5.1 Trade-off between resource utilization and PDV

Figure 5.2 Ideal use case with time-aligned reserved resources and the data arrival

Otherwise, as can be seen in Figure 5.1(b), in case of no overprovisioning of the resources, the PDV becomes significantly larger, and the maximum PD value is equal to the reserved resource period (the transmission time and propagation time are added on top of this value). The PD depends on the traffic pattern of the incoming traffic into the 5GS. Considering the two basic approaches of resource reservation in relation to incoming traffic, Figure 5.2 presents what the ideal case would be when a low allowed PDV is fulfilled without resource overprovisioning, because packets arrive just in time when reserved slots are available. However, in order to achieve this ideal scenario, the pattern of the incoming traffic into the 6GS needs to be perfectly aligned with the scheduling of the RAN, both in the periodicity and the scheduled start of the periodic transmission. Currently, there is neither alignment between the scheduling of the radio interface of the 5G and the application traffic transmission times, nor between their periodicities. An approach to address the described problem could be based on estimating traffic patterns from applications using E2E PD measurements to optimize RAN scheduling. These measurements could also be used to estimate clock drifts and periodicity mismatches. While ML could support in these estimations and optimizations, there would be a scalability challenge and a challenge to filter out delay-contributing sources, other than slot misalignment. With the high number of QoS flows in the network, estimating RAN scheduling for a specific QoS flow becomes difficult, especially given the dynamic nature of RAN scheduling. Without prior knowledge of these changes, a substantial portion of the limited and shared wireless channel resources would be consumed by additional traffic occupied for measuring and learning traffic patterns based on E2E PD measurements.

Previous work [KWC+22] addresses this topic but does not provide a comprehensive overview or detailed potential solutions. Therefore, in [HHA+24] and briefly in the following subsections, we describe how knowledge of traffic patterns could be systematically utilized within the 6GS and

externally, such as in TSN, to align traffic patterns with RAN scheduling. This alignment would minimize the number of occupied resources on the wireless channel.

5.1.2 3GPP support for periodic deterministic communication.

Overview

The 3GPP, from Release 16, describes enablers for TSN, TSC, time synchronization and DetNet, to support periodic deterministic communication [3GPP23-23501]. It specifies how traffic pattern characteristics known a priori can be communicated among the components within the 5GS and from external networks to the 5GS in specific cases. The TSC Assistance Information (TSCAI) is defined in Table 5.27.2-1 in [3GPP23-23501] and describes TSC traffic characteristics for use in the 5GS. It is an important enabler for the aforementioned problem. The TSC traffic pattern knowledge can be utilized by RAN to provide more efficient scheduling of QoS flows with periodic, deterministic traffic characteristics.

The determination of the TSC Assistance Container (TSCAC) based on Per-Stream Filtering and Policing (PSFP) information [IEEE22-8021Q] is applicable only to Ethernet-type Packet Data Unit (PDU) sessions and exclusively when integrated with TSN. PSFP information may be provided by the CNC if the TSN AF has indicated PSFP support to the CNC. Detailed descriptions of the flow of TSCAI-related data from the TSN AF to the RAN, as well as the RAN feedback parameters (time offset and adjusted periodicity) sent from the RAN to the TSN AF (in the case of TSN integration) or to the AF (in other cases, such as integration with DetNet), are provided in [HHA+24].

The TSCAI and RAN feedback parameters help reducing the delay between the arrival of traffic bursts and the next possible transmission over the wireless interface. They also help aligning the period of traffic bursts with the intervals of transmission opportunities on the wireless interface.

Challenges

The determination of TSCAI parameters in scenarios other than those based on PSFP, in the context of 5G integration with TSN, as well as the ways of forwarding RAN feedback parameters from 5G to external networks is outside the scope of 3GPP and has not been addressed so far. This indicates an opportunity for future work to define the transfer of TSCAI-relevant parameters between end users in external networks and the 6GS.

5.1.3 Proposed solutions for the flow of traffic pattern info through the 6GS and TSN network

We provided a description of the traffic specifications flow from applications via TSN network and how the feedback can be provided back to applications in [HHA+24]. In Figure 5.3, a block diagram of the integrated 6G-TSN architecture with the flow of TSCAC-relevant parameters (in blue) and RAN Feedback parameters (in red) is shown. The Traffic Specifications, Network Requirements and Interface Capabilities are defined by the user [IEEE17-8021Qcc].

This configuration is related to TSCAI parameters *capability for Burst Arrival Time (BAT) adaptation* and *periodicity range*. The TSCAI parameters such as *BAT* and *BAT window* can be calculated based on *EarliestTransmit* and *LatestTransmit* parameters from the Traffic Specifications. The Centralized User Configuration (CUC) controller reads these parameters from each end station over a user-level protocol, with a protocol such as Open Platform Communications - United Architecture (OPC-UA). The streams, selection of Talkers and Listeners and specifications of the application's timing requirements, e.g., periodic sending times are also designed by the CUC. This defines the interval at which Talkers transmit the data, and this parameter could be used as a TSCAI parameter *periodicity*. CUC then sends

the *interval* to end stations using a user-level protocol [IEEE17-8021Qcc]. This describes how the Traffic Specification parameters, related to some of TSCAI parameters can be transferred between the end stations/applications and the CUC.

Figure 5.3 6G-TSN integration with the flow of traffic pattern information

The CNC retrieves the TSN capabilities of each bridge using a Remote Network Management Protocol (RNMP), such as Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF), using YANG data models. It also receives the collected requirements and TSN capabilities of end stations from the CUC via the User-Network Interface (UNI), which describes the transfer of TSCAI-relevant parameters from the CUC to the CNC.

An alternative approach to extract TSCAI parameters is providing stream information, such as BAT and periodicity, directly as a service from the CNC to the TSN AF, encoded using YANG models [FVM20]. This solution eliminates the need for a new protocol or PSFP on both the 6GS and TSN sides. Additionally, the parameters provided through this method would offer higher precision compared to those derived from PSFP. The approach could also be generalized, allowing the 6G AF to subscribe to these parameters from an external network that gathers them from applications and provides them as a service. This describes the flow of TSCAI-relevant parameters from applications to the TSN AF.

The flow of TSCAC related parameters from TSN AF towards RAN and RAN feedback parameters towards TSN AF is briefly mentioned in Section 5.1.2 and more details are presented in [HHA+24]. As previously mentioned, the interface for transferring TSCAI feedback parameters from the TSN AF to the CNC does not exist. In this regard, a key architectural characteristic in the fully centralized TSN configuration is that the CNC as a central entity can only send scheduling configurations but cannot receive feedback. However, when RAN feedback parameters are provided by the TSN AF, the CNC would need to receive scheduling-related instructions or suggestions from the 6G TSN bridge. These parameters, however, do not directly impact the CNC's configuration but should instead be forwarded to the CUC. The CNC's configuration is indirectly influenced when updated traffic specifications are received from end stations via the CUC in the next iteration, after which the CNC may send modified interface configurations to bridges and end stations.

A potential solution is to establish a subscription-based interface where the CNC, or even directly the CUC, subscribes to the TSN AF service that provides the RAN feedback parameters. Another option

could involve adding additional parameters, such as extended interface capabilities, which the CNC can retrieve from each 6G TSN bridge via the RNMP.

If the RAN feedback parameters are available at the CNC, they could be forwarded to the CUC along with the status of each stream via the UNI. This status includes the success or failure of each stream's configuration and the interface configuration for each end station. In the case of a failure, the CUC might adjust its requirements and retry with updated traffic specifications informed by the RAN feedback parameters, such as the BAT offset. This offset could be provided as a parameter within the status information received from the CNC.

The CUC provides the Interface Configuration details for each stream to the end stations. Using this information, an end station can configure its application to ensure that different streams are transmitted in a specific order, aligning with the expected reserved resources on the network, specifically on the wireless interface of the 5G/6G. The CUC can define the initial configuration, manage changes in an operational network, or both. It communicates with the end stations using managed objects as specified in [IEEE24-8021Qdj]. This describes the RAN feedback parameters flow from the CNC to the end stations/applications, which is highlighted in Figure 5.3 in red line.

5.1.4 Scenarios with the support of TSCAI feature

As explained in Section 5.1.1, the TSCAI feature could decrease the number of occupied resources on the wireless interface of the 6GS and minimize the PD and PDV in use cases where the traffic pattern characteristics are known a priori, specifically in cases of periodic traffic transmissions. An example of a use case where the knowledge of the traffic pattern would be useful is presented in Figure 5.1, where the required maximum PD and the PDV is smaller than the period of the traffic. The described TSCAI feature and/or RAN feedback could be utilized during the admission control phase on startup of an application, therefore it is assumed that many applications are able to shift the start of their transmission time and/or to adjust the periodicity. On the other hand, there could be applications where the shift in time or periodicity would not be feasible due to strict constraint on synchronization with external systems and other process control loops.

For the plots in Figure 5.4, the OMNET++ platform is used for simulations while the measurements are carried out in an experimental factory floor, as described in [HHM+23]. Both OMNET++ simulations and 5G testbed measurements results provide the one-way PD in time. Both setup configurations have the TDD pattern DDDDDDDUU, 30 kHz subcarrier spacing, packet size of 50 bytes and sending period of 10 ms. In both simulation and measurement setups, the sender and receiver applications are synchronized. However, there we introduced an offset of 200 ppm between the packet sending period and the 5G frame duration to clearly visualize the delay components. Both setups use the grant-based scheduling procedure because the CG approach has not been available in the 5G testbed setup. The difference compared to the CG scheduling approach is the additional grant-procedure delay, which is highlighted in Figure 5.4 as a black dotted line. The purpose of the measurement and simulation results is to show that the simulated delay patterns are consistent with the delay patterns in the real 5G system, where we can clearly see the queuing delay variation pattern related to the alignment of the traffic pattern with the RAN frame-slot arrangement. In the following, we focus on a CG scheduling approach for the periodic traffic. It is important to note that there is a significant delay contribution from retransmissions, as highlighted in red in Figure 5.4. However, as mentioned earlier, this delay contribution is not the focus of this work, and mechanisms to deal with it are mentioned in Section

5.1.1. In the following subsections, we present several scenarios where the TSCAI could be used to decrease the PD and PDV.

(a) Simulation results

(b) 5G testbed measurement results

Figure 5.4 Comparison of simulation with measurements in grant-based transmissions

5.1.5 Fixed time offset between the application traffic bursts and the allocated RAN resources

A scenario where the TSCAI information can minimize the PD is in the case of a fixed time offset between the application traffic arrival and the reserved resources on the wireless interface. This is the scenario where the 6GS and the external network are perfectly synchronized in time and the period of the application traffic is the same or a multiple of the period of the reserved resources on the wireless interface within the RAN.

Figure 5.5 A scenario with fixed time offset between the traffic and RAN scheduled resources

This scenario is shown in the time domain of the simulation results in Figure 5.5. The blue line shows the uplink (UL) E2E PD in case there is no alignment between the traffic bursts and the RAN scheduling (a traffic burst arrives periodically every 10 ms and each time wait 4 ms before the transmission until a scheduled resources are reached. The remaining 1 ms is modeled as processing and propagation delay), while the orange line shows the scenario if the TSCAI parameters were provided to the 6GS. Either RAN modifies the scheduled resources accordingly or provides the RAN feedback parameter and the application changes its burst sending time. This results in traffic bursts reaching the scheduled resources without waiting in the buffer before the transmission. The 1 ms PD, modeled as a fixed value in the ideal case, represents the propagation and processing delay.

5.1.6 Misalignment of the application traffic bursts periodicity and the allocated RAN resources

The second scenario where the TSCAI feature could improve the PDV is when there is a mismatch between the periodicity of the application traffic and the reserved resources on the wireless interface. In this scenario, the application traffic is sent periodically every 11.5 ms, while the resources are reserved with a period of 5 ms.

Figure 5.6 Scenario with periodicity misalignment between traffic bursts and scheduled resources

The mismatch between these two periodicities causes significant PDV, as traffic bursts arrive at varying slots relative to the start of a frame, whereas the reserved resources remain fixed at specific slots relative to the frame's start. Such a scenario can be seen in Figure 5.6. If the TSCAI feature is used, and either the RAN aligns its scheduling according to the periodicity parameter, or the application adjusts its traffic burst period based on the feedback parameter *adjusted periodicity* from the RAN, the alignment can be achieved which results in an ideal case presented in Figure 5.5 (orange line). Comparing the case with a mismatch with an ideal case, we can see that, in the ideal case, we can decrease the PD from 5.5 ms to 1 ms (1 ms is the modeled processing and propagation delay).

5.1.7 Clock drift between the 6GS and the external network

The third scenario where the TSCAI can improve the PD and PDV is when there is a drift or offset between the 6G clock and an external network clock. The effect of the clock drift is similar to the misalignment of the transmission and scheduled resource periods, explained in the previous subsection, however, clock drift usually means much smaller misalignment. In [HHA+24] we described that based on the reports from the UPF, the 6G Session Management Function (SMF) compensates the clock drift by modifying the values of relevant TSCAI parameters going to RAN, or the RAN feedback parameters, coming from RAN. A scenario with realistic clock drift effect can be seen in Figure 5.7, while Figure 5.4 represents an example of a fixed clock offset. An ideal scenario after the SMF corrections is shown already in Figure 5.5 (orange line). Comparing the cases with clock drifts

with an ideal case, we can see that, in the ideal case, we can decrease the PD from 6 ms to 1 ms (1 ms is the modeled processing and propagation delay).

Moreover, the TSCAI feature can compensate also for a combination of the discussed scenarios, including the traffic offset, periodicity mismatch and clock drift, which is the most common in real-world scenarios.

Figure 5.7 Clock drift between 6GS and an external network

5.1.8 Key takeaways

In this section we targeted the queuing PD in cellular communications, originating from a misalignment of periodic traffic arrival time instances and the scheduled reserved resources, which results in significant PDV. It is important to note that there is the standardization support for periodic deterministic communication in the context of alignment of the traffic sending time with the scheduled resources in the 5G-TSN system was highlighted. However, the challenges and missing interfaces were discovered and enhancements for resource optimization to increase the traffic capacity with decreased PD and PDV were proposed. We outlined the E2E flow of the TSCAI parameters from applications, via TSN network to the RAN within the 6GS, and the flow of the RAN feedback in the opposite direction. Finally, we presented the improvements of the PD and PDV, based on measurement and simulation results across various scenarios in case the TSCAI, RAN Feedback and stream information parameters are used as discussed throughout this section.

5.2 Dependable 6G using environmental-aware reinforcement learning-based scheduling strategy

The next generation of wireless networks (6G) aims to deliver advanced capabilities, making these networks dependable. The broad meaning of dependability is that a network consistently is performing as expected, meaning that a dependable network can quantitatively ascertain that it will deliver the required service performance for the network services according to the performance level(s) that were agreed upon. Achieving this involves: (i) assessing dependability through network configuration and (ii) enhancing it through optimizations during network operation. One of the aspects that can significantly improve dependability is network scheduling and resource allocation when optimized while having dependability aspects in mind [KN23]. In this section, we introduce a novel scheduling strategy that combines Reinforcement Learning (RL) with environmental knowledge to enhance reliability and availability aspects of dependability.

5.2.1 Overview

Network schedulers have typically been optimized based on conventional Network Performance Indicators (NPIs) like throughput and communication delay. In [DET23-D31], the scheduler-related topic was in the context of calculating the wireless friendly E2E schedules considering stochastic PD with high PDV. There, the focus was specifically on Time-Aware Shaper (TAS), used for scheduled traffic in TSN, specified in IEEE 802.1Qbv. Although these NPIs are crucial indicators, effective resource allocation and network scheduling can significantly enhance network's dependability, when optimized defining new metrics referred to as Dependability Indicators (DIs). Centered on PHY layer parameters, in this work two measurable DIs are defined, namely *service reliability* and *service availability*, and the goal is to enhance them through network scheduling. Here, service reliability ensures that the system provides the required connectivity service without failure, and service availability refers to the system's ability to provide uninterrupted connectivity services based on specific requests. When attempting to enhance both service reliability and availability, we encounter a conflicting multi-objective optimization problem, as improving one often compromises the other. As a solution to this, we propose a deep RL-based scheduling strategy with the goal to balance reliability and availability and at the same time keep fairness, which is one of the key NPIs. In addition, recent advancements in approaches like Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) have demonstrated significant potential for improving environmental awareness, a key factor in optimizing communication networks due to the substantial impact of environmental changes on PHY parameters. Building on this, we have integrated environmental-aware knowledge into the design of the scheduling strategy. Further details on this work can be found in the published paper [BKS+24].

5.2.2 Related work

Numerous studies have explored model-based network scheduling algorithms. The most known algorithms are the classical schedulers Round Robin (RR) and Proportional Fair (PF). The RR method cycles through all nodes sequentially regardless of channel conditions or data requirements and in this way ensures fairness. The PF scheduler seeks a balance between maximizing network throughput and ensuring a fair allocation of resources among users [MFG+22]. Building on these foundational methods, advanced intelligent scheduling approaches leveraging machine learning, particularly RL, have emerged to address the limitations of classical algorithms and further optimize traditional NPIs. For instance, [ZTK+20] introduced an RL-based resource allocation algorithm that incorporates multiple network parameters and accounts for future states during learning. Similarly, [DSH+21] proposed a deep learning framework that minimizes base station (BS) power consumption by optimizing bandwidth and transmit power, employing a cascaded Neural Network (NN) structure to meet QoS requirements and applying deep transfer learning for non-stationary environments. There are several more studies that propose various scheduling strategies tailored to specific scenarios such as high mobility [XHC+22], heterogeneous industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) [MRC+24] that have in common RL strategies combined with either feature extraction for traffic analysis or consider some kind of prediction for traffic volume.

5.2.3 Environmental-aware knowledge

Wireless communication performance is heavily influenced by the radio propagation environment. Environmental awareness has recently gained attention and is expected to play an important role in further enhancing network performance in terms of high reliability, low latency, and massive connectivity by providing precision in the estimation/prediction of the channel instantaneously. This can be achieved through various sensing technologies like radar, camera, LiDAR, GPS, and Ultra-Wide

Band (UWB). For instance, Channel Knowledge Maps (CKM) provide location-specific channel information [ZX21], while multi-modal sensing can predict channel conditions and detect objects by integrating multiple inputs [COH+22]. Following the concept of CKM, this work focuses on the obstacle detection capability of the system, providing a binary spatial map of Line of Sight (LOS) and Non-Line of Sight (NLOS) states of moving nodes in a given area, which we refer to as the environmental-aware map. It is important to note that LOS/NLOS is just one example of input knowledge. The spatial map can be generated using any other QoS parameters (e.g., [AB22], [HHM+23]), which can then be transformed into a binary decision by applying thresholds based on the required service bounds.

5.2.4 A novel RL-based scheduling system

We propose an RL-based scheduler which tries to allocate the resource blocks among K nodes in such a way that the overall network dependability in terms of reliability and availability is enhanced while maintaining fairness among the nodes. The proposed scheduler, illustrated in Figure 5.8, utilizes environment-driven knowledge as the input data to create a resource allocation policy that maximizes the metrics defined for assessing the network’s dependability.

Figure 5.8 The proposed environmental-aware RL scheduler methodology

In the proposed method, an RL agent observes the environment’s state, denoted as $S(t)$, and selects the action $a(t) \in 1, \dots, K$ with the highest expected reward. This action influences the immediate rewards $r(t)$ received and alters the environment’s state. With a single-user scheduling scenario, the agent’s task is to choose one node to serve at each Transmission Time Interval (TTI). The environmental-aware knowledge gives details on the LOS/NLOS states of the k th moving node, $k = 1, \dots, K$, at current TTI as $s(t, k)$. It also includes predictions for these states over the next T TTIs, as $s(t + i, k)$, $i = 1, \dots, T$, assuming the trajectories of the nodes are estimated for T upcoming TTIs. In addition, the number of TTIs that the k th node has been served within the previous L TTIs is tracked and stored as $h(k, t)$. Therefore, the state of the environment in our problem at TTI t is defined as $S(t)$ with dimension $K \times (T + 2)$ and the k th row as

$$s(k, t) = [h(k, t), s(t, k), s(t + 1, k), \dots, s(t + T, k)].$$

Due to the extensive number of states in our problem, the Deep Q-Network (DQN) algorithm with an online three layer-NN, parameterized by θ is deployed to approximate the action-value function. Another NN with the same structure but a different parameter set θ^- , is used to approximate the target value. The online NN is updated at the i th iteration based on the difference between the estimated value and the target value as

$$L(\theta_i) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a,r(t),s')} \left[\left(r(t) + \gamma \max Q_\theta - (s', a') - Q_{\theta_i}(s, a) \right)^2 \right],$$

Where $s, a, r(t), s'$, and γ are the current state, action, immediate reward, the next state, and discount factor, respectively. The immediate reward $r(t)$ is what the agent receives as feedback on how good or bad was the selected action in terms of the defined metrics. More details on how this reward function is designed in our problem will be given later in this section. In addition, the target network is also updated every number of episodes as $\theta^- \leftarrow \theta$.

At each TTI, the agent uses an ε -greedy policy: it selects the action with the maximum estimated value with probability $1 - \varepsilon$ or a random action with probability ε . The value of ε starts as ε_{max} and decreases over time to shift from exploration to exploitation, with ε_{min} set to limit further exploration.

Defined metrics

The ultimate goal of the proposed scheduler is to enhance the reliability and availability aspects of dependability throughout the network based on two metrics, respectively, service reliability and service availability, while maintaining fairness in the network. Considering only one node is served at each TTI, the service reliability metric is defined as

$$\mathbb{E}_t[\text{Rel}] = \mathbb{E}_t \left[\sum_{k=1}^K z(t, k) \text{Rel}(t, k) \right],$$

with $z(t, k) = 1$ if the k th node is served at TTI t , otherwise $z(t, k) = 0$, and $\text{Rel}(t, k)$ is the k th node reliability score at TTI t . In a noise-limited scenario, we consider the state of LOS/NLOS as a binary parameter that can indicate service reliability at node k during TTI t as

$$\text{Rel}(t, k) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } s(t, k) \equiv \text{LOS} \\ 0 & \text{if } s(t, k) \equiv \text{NLOS} \end{cases}$$

Service availability is defined as

$\mathbb{E}_t[\text{Avl}] = \mathbb{E}_t \left[\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \text{Avl}(t, k) \right]$, with $\text{Avl}(t, k)$ as the k th node's availability at time t which is calculated as

$$\text{Avl}(t, k) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } TBA(t, k) \leq \zeta \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Here, $TBA(t, k)$ is Time Between Accesses (TBA) and denotes the number of TTIs that have passed since the k th node last accessed the network, recorded at TTI t . Specifically, if the k th node is served at TTI t , then $TBA(t, k)$ is zero, otherwise it increases by one. In the previous equation, ζ is the maximum number of allowed TTIs between accesses. If a node's TBA exceeds this threshold, its service is deemed unavailable. Finally, the last metric is fairness and is calculated as defined in [PSB19]:

$$\mathbb{E}_t[\text{Fair}] = \mathbb{E}_t \left[\frac{\left(\sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\tau=t-L}^t z(\tau, k) \right)^2}{K \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\sum_{\tau=t-L}^t z(\tau, k) \right)^2} \right].$$

Reward function

According to the defined evaluation metrics, the reward function is defined as follows

$$r(t) = c_1 \widehat{\text{Rel}}(t) + c_2 \widehat{\text{Avl}}(t) + c_3 \widehat{\text{Fair}}(t),$$

where $\widehat{\text{Rel}}(t)$, $\widehat{\text{Avl}}(t)$ and $\widehat{\text{Fair}}(t)$ are respectively reliability, availability, and fairness-related rewards with c_1, c_2, c_3 as constants. If a node with a service reliability score of one is chosen at TTI t , the agent receives a positive reward of c_1 . If no nodes have a service reliability score of one, no reward related to service reliability is given, i.e. $\widehat{\text{Rel}}(t) = 0$. However, if the agent selects a node with a service reliability score of zero while there exists at least one node with a reliability score of one, the agent receives a negative reward of $-c_1$.

To improve service availability, it is essential to reduce TBA for all nodes. Prioritizing nodes that are transitioning from LOS to NLOS based on their movement trajectories is key, as delaying their service can lower their future service reliability. Thus, the agent gains $c_2 \widehat{\text{Avl}}(t) = \frac{c_2}{\sum_{i=1}^T s(t+i, a(t))}$ for choosing nodes with a reliability score of one that is likely to move to NLOS within the next T TTIs. Otherwise, the service availability-related reward would be zero. Finally, the fairness-related reward is the actual fairness score that the taken action archives as $\widehat{\text{Fair}}(t) = \text{Fair}(t)$.

5.2.5 Performance evaluation

We consider an indoor industrial environment and downlink communication in a 5G cellular network with R Remote Radio Heads (RRHs) and K nodes. It is assumed that the Base Station (BS) unit can generate an environmental-aware map and can also predict it for the near future, based on the side information about the environment, including the node positions, movement directions, etc. To generate environmental-aware maps, we consider the Geometry-based Stochastic Channel Model (GSCM) from 3GPP TR 38.901 [3GPP24-38901], tailored to an indoor factory scenario. This scenario focuses on factory halls of different sizes and varying clutter densities (e.g. machines, storage shelves, assembly lines, etc.). This model allows for various geometrical factors, including the height of RRHs located either above the clutter (very high) or embedded within it (low height), as well as the height of the factory hall, and the dimension of clutter. In addition to the 3GPP TR 38.901 [3GPP24-38901] indoor factory scenario, we incorporated the spatial consistency adapted from [AMS+17], [ASB+19] into the model. This model adaptation is necessary for accurately reflecting spatial correlation, ensuring that closely located nodes in the factory floor experience similar channel propagation effects, due to shared scatterers in the environment.

Environmental-aware map for LOS/NLOS

We focus on one of the environment properties, the state of being in LOS/NLOS propagation, where for node k and TTI t , the LOS/NLOS state is obtained as

$$s(t, k) = \begin{cases} \text{LOS}, & \text{if } q(t, k) \leq p_{\text{LOS}}(t, k) \\ \text{NLOS}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

Where p_{LOS} denotes the probability of being in LOS, which is a function of the link between nodes and the closest RRH considering both distance and height, and $q(t, k)$ are spatially correlated random variables for any t and k adapted from the methodology in [AMS+17]. Figure 5.9 illustrates one example of a binary environmental-aware map for an area of $300 \times 150 \text{ m}^2$ and a resolution of 0.5 m. We consider 18 RRHs, denoted in green circles, spaced on a square lattice with spacing D , located $D/2$ from the walls (see Table 5.2). White color denotes LOS state and black color denotes NLOS state.

Figure 5.9 Environmental-aware map with LOS/NLOS states for a factory floor with clutter density of 35%.

The generated binary environmental-aware map is the input to the proposed environmental-aware scheduler. Note that the ratio between LOS/NLOS depends on the system parameters such as the clutter density, clutter size and height as well as RRH location, which are inferred in the statistics of the GSCM.

Scheduler evaluation

We evaluate the performance of the proposed scheduler with two well-studied scheduling methods in the literature, the RR and PF schedulers [MFG+22], where RR schedules the nodes in the best fairness manner while PF tries to improve the overall throughput (which in our scenario results in the service reliability enhancement).

Table 5.2 Simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Number of RRHs (R)	18
Distance between RRHs (D)	50 m
Ceiling height	10 m
Clutter height	5 m
Clutter density (μ)	10% – 80%
Clutter size	5 m
Node height	1.5 m
RRH height for low RRH	1.5 m
RRH height for high RRH	8 m
Number of nodes (K)	5
History length (L) [TTI]	10
Prediction length (T) [TTI]	10
$\epsilon_{\max}, \epsilon_{\min}$	1, 0.0001
c_1, c_2, c_3	10, 10, 5
Discount factor (γ)	0.95
Learning rate	0.1

Table 5.2 shows a summary of simulation parameters, where the parameters related to the geometry of the factory floor are taken from 3GPP TR 38.901 [3GPP24-38901]. The deployed model is trained for 1000 iterations, while a new 300 m \times 150 m 2D-map is generated independently for each iteration, with random node locations and movement trajectories initialization. For simplicity, all nodes share the same traffic parameters and have the same service requirements. Figure 5.10 illustrates the cumulative reward progression over 1000 iterations for the proposed algorithm. Early iterations exhibit significant reward fluctuations as the agent explores and performs random actions. Gradually,

the agent learns to associate states with optimal actions, leading to improved and more consistent rewards.

Figure 5.10 Cumulative reward per iteration

We look at three aspects as defined in Section 5.2.4, reliability, availability and fairness. In addition, to provide a single metric for comparing the performance of the three methods, we use a cumulative evaluation index called Δ , adopted from [XHC+22], and defined as

$$\Delta = \Delta^{\text{Rel}} + \Delta^{\text{Avl}} + \Delta^{\text{Fair}},$$

where

$$\Delta^j = \frac{y_{i,j} - \bar{y}_j}{v_j},$$

With $y_{i,j}$ representing the specific value of algorithm i in terms of j th evaluation metric, including service reliability, service availability, and fairness; \bar{y}_j and v_j are respectively the average and standard deviation values of the j th metric across all algorithms.

Figure 5.11 compares the achieved performance when RRHs are clutter embedded with a height of 1.5 m. The results are evaluated over the clutter density $\mu = \{10\%, 20\%, \dots, 80\%\}$. As expected, PF and the proposed method significantly outperform RR in terms of service reliability, whereas in terms of service availability, RR is superior closely followed by the proposed algorithms. Only for clutter density $\mu \leq 50\%$, RR slightly outperforms our proposed method, revealing that the proposed method is advantageous when there are more blockages on the factory floor. Considering fairness, the proposed and RR algorithms perform similarly and noticeably better than PF. When comparing all three aspects, defined by Δ , the proposed algorithm is superior for all cases when $\mu \geq 20\%$, denoting environments with an increase of NLOS areas.

Figure 5.11 Performance results for the scenario with low RRH height (1.5 m) and clutter density $\mu = \{10\%, 20\%, \dots, 80\%\}$.

Figure 5.12 shows the same comparison when RRHs have a height of 8 m. Similarly, PF and the proposed method significantly outperform RR in terms of service reliability, however achieving higher reliability as compared to the low RRH height scenario. In terms of both service availability and fairness, the proposed algorithm and RR perform closely, surpassing PF. When comparing all three aspects, defined by the Δ , the proposed algorithm is superior for all cases when $\mu \geq 32\%$, making the proposed method ideal for blockage-prone factory floors. As the algorithm is designed to share resources and prioritize serving nodes depending on the prediction and history of LOS/NLOS states, it does perform poorly only when most nodes are in LOS most of the time - which is not realistic for factory floor environments.

Figure 5.12 Performance results for the scenario with high RRH height (8 m) and clutter density $\mu = \{10\%, 20\%, \dots, 80\%\}$.

5.2.6 Key takeaways

This RL-based, environmental-aware scheduling strategy enhances the defined dependability aspects by leveraging real-world network conditions to optimize reliability, availability, and fairness in dynamic environments. Unlike traditional schedulers that focus solely on NPIs like throughput and delay, this approach integrates environmental awareness to make intelligent scheduling decisions based on real-time conditions such as LOS/NLOS states. By using a Deep Q-Network (DQN), the scheduler learns to balance competing objectives, ensuring stable and continuous service even in challenging, high-obstruction environments. The results show that this method significantly outperforms classical scheduling strategies, particularly in scenarios with high clutter density where changes from LOS to NLOS are very frequent, demonstrating its potential for future 6G deployments where dependability is critical.

5.3 Interactive feedback between RAN scheduling and E2E TSN scheduler

A central component of TSN's determinism is its scheduling framework. Defined in IEEE 802.1Qbv [IEEE15-8021Qbv], this framework specifies how to use Gate Control Lists (GCLs) to maintain strictly controlled transmission times and avoid unwanted contention (for a description of 802.1Qbv, see Section 1.4.2). In practice, the Centralized Network Configuration controller (CNC), informed by the

Centralized User Configuration controller (CUC), orchestrates end-to-end scheduling by generating GCLs and distributing them to TSN bridges. By imposing a structured timeline on traffic flows, the TSN architecture forms a stable, deterministic communication fabric, precisely governing when and how data is transmitted throughout the network.

Extending TSN principles into wireless domains introduces a new set of challenges due to the inherently variable and stochastic nature of radio channels. While TSN standards such as IEEE 802.1Qbv include well-defined tools to realize deterministic performance over wired Ethernet, providing similar guarantees over wireless links requires careful adaptation. A central assumption in TSN with respect to the bridge behavior are transfer times in the range of 100s of nanoseconds, as well as the possibility to manage transfer times deterministically. This is in strong contrast to how wireless 5G systems behave, necessitating the integration of 5G systems into TSN to be more dynamically managed due to the fluctuating latency. This leads to collaboration between the CNC and the 5G network, leveraging adaptive scheduling and resource management to preserve TSN's deterministic objectives over the wireless medium.

DETERMINISTIC6G has been addressing these issues through Packet Delay Correction (PDC), as described in Section 2 and in Deliverable 2.1 [DET23-D21]. By observing and correcting delay variations in the 5G/6G networks, packet delay variations can be eliminated (at the cost of an increase in absolute delay), turning the 5G/6G network into a node with deterministic delay performance (similar to a wired node) but with comparatively large absolute delay (compared to a wired node). From a TSN CNC perspective, this turns the 5G/6G system into a virtual node that can be handled like any wired TSN bridge, and also enables scalable, reliable and deterministic communication over wireless TSN domains.

Another approach developed in DETERMINISTIC6G is a new TSN scheduling method of Full Interleaving Packet Scheduling (FIPS), see Section 3.4 in Deliverable D3.4 [DET24-D34]. FIPS is a robust scheduling mechanism that dynamically incorporates for instance periodically updated per-flow stochastic packet delay characterizations provided by the 5G/6G network. By leveraging this data, FIPS can adapt to the inherent variability of wireless environments, allowing it to maintain determinism despite stochastic delays. Its design permits controlled interleaving of transmissions, thereby optimizing resource usage and relaxing the strict temporal isolation constraints that are typically enforced in wired TSN. In cases of significant network disruptions, FIPS ensures graceful degradation by prioritizing critical traffic while lowering the quality of service for lower-priority flows, thereby preventing data loss. As a wireless-friendly enhancement to IEEE 802.1Qbv scheduling, FIPS provides a foundation for achieving scalable, reliable, and deterministic communication over wireless TSN domains.

A central question emerges in this context how a 5G/6G system should interact with FIPS. While FIPS offers significant improvements for TSN scheduling in dynamic wireless environments, it faces the limitation that it requires stochastic delay characterizations of the 5G/6G system. These delay characterizations require generally detailed information about the internals of 5G/6G systems, which generally cannot be assumed to be available to a TSN CNC. In contrast to ex-post delay histograms, two aspects arise in this context in particular: (1) Insufficient conditioning of per-flow delay histograms, and (2) lack of predictive modeling. Overcoming these challenges is essential for ensuring truly deterministic, reliable, and scalable end-to-end communication in 5G/6G-enabled TSN systems. We discuss some more details on these aspects below:

- First, ex-post histograms may not fully capture all relevant system-level dependencies in 5G/6G networks. For example, factors such as the TDD pattern, numerology, and resource allocation strategies can clearly influence the observed latencies and reliabilities. Meanwhile, the effects of other parameters—such as the number of admitted flows or the choice of modulation and coding schemes—may vary depending on specific implementation and scheduling mechanisms, and their overall impact on latency or reliability is not always straightforward. As a result, relying solely on ex-post histograms can overlook important system interactions, and closer coordination between TSN and 5G/6G (along with more comprehensive modeling) is advisable to enable more effective scheduling decisions.
- Second, ex-post histograms only capture stochastic behavior of the past and have potentially only limited predictive power for the next scheduling period. It is worthwhile noting here that FIPS might reconsider assigned scheduled in the range of minutes or hours, while 5G/6G systems allocate resources and perform dynamic packet scheduling on a millisecond base, due to the dynamic nature of wireless propagation environments. It is therefore necessary to expand 5G/6G stochastic characterizations towards the long scheduling periods of the TSN domain, which involves an element of stochastic prediction. Transitioning from purely descriptive to predictive models – supported by forecasting techniques – would enable proactive adjustments to network conditions, thereby improving determinism. These predictions could be further supplemented by digital twins. Ideally, predictions can be further supplemented by uncertainty measures.

Beyond these immediate challenges, the question also arises how a TSN domain with FIPS should interact in the scheduling phase with 5G/6G systems. While a centralized approach would require the formulation of a joint optimization problem, this would necessitate a large amount of 5G/6G-internal data to be transferred to that decision-making FIPS entity. Contrarily, a large amount of TSN-specific state information would have to be exposed to a 5G/6G system if a joint FIPS was to be executed within the 5G/6G domain. Nevertheless, from an optimality point of view it is interesting and challenging to formulate such an entity and solve for performance comparison purposes.

A more realistic implementation will likely see iterations between the TSN domain and the 5G/6G domain (see Figure 5.13). A framework is currently under preparation, where precise mathematical formulations will be developed together with heuristics in particular for the 5G/6G domain. In such an iterative framework (see Figure 5.13 for a flow chart of the operations), the CNC could supply each flow's requirements (as informed by the CUC) directly to the 5G/6G network. The cellular domain would then manage admission control, establish packet delay budgets (PDBs), and dynamically adjust configurations to maintain determinism. By transferring complexity to the 5G/6G domain, this approach leverages the network's native intelligence and adaptability, resulting in more stable and accurate delay predictions and improved overall performance. All these issues are for future work.

Figure 5.13 Interactions between the TSN domain and the 5G/6G domain.

6 Conclusion

6G is deemed as a key technology to support emerging applications with stringent requirements for a highly dependable and time-critical communication. This document reports on 6G-centric enablers that will be crucial to realize these future needs. In particular, the focus is on new features required within the 6G system to both handle or compensate for its stochastic behavior and to adapt dynamically the network configurations by using the best possible data-driven latency prediction models and architecture.

One of the proposals is to compensate for the intrinsic 6G Packet Delay Variation (PDV) that several applications are unable to correct and cannot tolerate. To achieve this goal Packet Delay Correction (PDC) has been proposed by this project and several alternative realization variants have been developed. This report proposes a new PDC designed for periodic traffic and discusses a qualitative evaluation of all PDCs so far in order to bring to light the strengths and applicability of every method. Evaluations through simulations have also been included showing a good PDV control when PDC is used. In particular, considering PDCs based on timestamps and virtual timeslots, the benefits and impact of PDC deployment is captured in terms of on-time delivery and number of schedulable TSN streams.

On data-driven characterization of 6G performance, prediction methods play an important role as enabler of dependability and autonomous network adaptation. To do so, predictability (the ability to predict) is mathematically defined and modelled for general multi-hop systems. Analysis of this framework leads to multiple learning, among which it is shown that network monitoring and observability are crucial for preserving a good level of predictability. Going further into data-driven latency characterization, this report introduces a probabilistic delay prediction approach based on deep temporal models which considers the dynamics in 5G/6G integrated with TSN. Through evaluations it is demonstrated that Transformers are best suited for capturing long-term dependencies.

Data collection is a prerequisite for latency prediction which is relevant for defining learning architectures and is enabled by an observability framework. To this end, architectural aspects regarding learning approaches and observability are studied here. In this report, it is studied how multiple factors of wireless and ML parameters affect the total training time of different learning architectures, such as centralized and federated learning. When evaluating the overhead of these learning architectures, it is shown that increasing the number of local epochs reduces inverse-proportionally the total training time. For this reason, it is important to set the number of local epochs by considering the accuracy and the total training time. Another architectural aspect is related to performance measurements. Measuring the delay performance is relevant for both enabling observability and as input for data-driven characterization for further performance prediction and network adaptability. As mentioned, observability is also key to enable a good level of predictability as concluded in the mathematical predictability model. To realize observability, this report discusses the architectural changes needed to acquire and distribute performance measurements.

Additional 6G-centric approaches can be applied in order to maximize the network service for applications with stringent QoS KPIs. The solution in this sense could rely on an optimized radio resource management. Three approaches are proposed and analyzed in this report. For the first approach, the idea is to align RAN scheduling with the traffic characteristics of the applications where insights on how to exchange such information could be realized in the 6G network. Just as with PDC,

this is a scheme that manipulates the flow within the 6G system in order to achieve the sought performance by adjusting to delivery requirements of the flows. For the second approach, optimized availability and reliability can be achieved by using reinforcement models that enable RAN scheduling to consider environmental parameters. And finally for the third approach, a mechanism is envisioned to allow interactions between the E2E TSN scheduler and the 6G RAN scheduler. This report discusses that feedback provided from 6G RAN to the TSN scheduler would allow for promising E2E performance optimization.

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8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: List of abbreviations

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5GAA	5G Automotive Association
5G-Adv	5G-Advanced
5GC	5G Core Network
5GS	5G System
5QI	5G QoS Identifier
6GS	6G System
ACL	Access Control List
AF	Application Function
AGV	Automatic Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BAT	Burst Arrival Time
BLER	Block Error Rate
BS	Base Station
CDE	Conditional Density Estimation
CG	Configured Grant
CKM	Channel Knowledge Maps
CL	Centralized Learning
CNC	Centralized Network Configuration controller
CPS	Cyber-Physical System
CQF	Cyclic Queueing and Forwarding
CUC	Centralized User Configuration controller
DetNet	Deterministic Networking
DL	Downlink
DQN	Deep Q-Network
DS-TT	Device-side TT
E2E	End-to-end
EDAF	End-to-End Delay Analytics Framework
FIPS	Full Interleaving Packet Scheduling
FL	Federated Learning
FT	Forwarding Time
gNB	Next Generation Node B
GCL	Gate Control List
GMM	Gaussian Mixture Model
GPRS	Generalized Packet Radio Service

gPTP	Generalized PTP
GSCM	Geometry-based Stochastic Channel Model
GTP-U	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol for User plane data
H&F	Hold and Forward buffering mechanism
HARQ	Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request
HI	High-load learning
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LO	Low-load learning
LOS	Line of Sight
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory networks
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MAC	Medium Access Control
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
MDN	Mixture Density Network
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptrons
NETCONF	Network Configuration Protocol
NLL	Negative Log-Likelihood
NLOS	No-Line of Sight
NN	Neural Network
NPI	Network Performance Indicator
NW-TT	Network-side TT
OAM	Operations Administration and Maintenance
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing
OMM	Observable Markov Model
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications - United Architecture
PD	Packet Delay
PDC	Packet Delay Correction
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PDU	Protocol Data Unit
PDV	Packet Delay Variation
PE	Permutation Entropy
PF	Proportional Fair
PHY	Physical
PLC	Programmable Logical Controller
PMF	Probability Mass Function
PRB	Physical Resource Block

PSFP	Per-Stream Filtering and Policing
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
Qbv	IEEE 802.1Qbv, Scheduled Traffic
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RNMP	Remote Network Management Protocol
RR	Round Robin
RRH	Remote Radio Head
SDAP	Service Data Adaption Protocol
SDR	Software-Defined Radio
SFN	System Frame Number
SINR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
SMF	Session Management Function
TAS	Time-Aware Shaper
TBA	Time Between Accesses
TDD	Time Division Duplex
TSC	Time-Sensitive Communications
TSCAC	TSC Assistance Container
TSCAI	TSC Assistance Information
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
TSN AF	TSN Application Function
TT	TSN Translator
TTI	Transmission Time Interval
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
UNI	User-Network Interface
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra Reliable and Low Latency Communication
UWB	Ultra-Wide Band
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation model